

**KNOWLEDGE, ATTITUDE AND PRACTICES OF MOTHERS ON SEVEN KEY
CHILD SURVIVAL INTERVENTIONS IN ABEOKUTA SOUTH AND ODEDA LOCAL
GOVERNMENT AREA.**

BY

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MATRIC NUMBER 2013/1540

A project report

Submitted to the Department of Nutrition and Dietetics.

**Federal University of Agriculture, Abeokuta, Nigeria, In Partial Fulfillment of the
Requirement for the Award of Degree of Bachelor of Science in Nutrition and Dietetics.**

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JANUARY, 2017

CERTIFICATION

This is to certify that this project work was carried out by MAYAKI TOMISIN BLESSING and is approved in partial fulfillment of the requirement for award of B. Sc degree in Nutrition and Dietetics of the Department of Nutrition and Dietetics, College of Food and Human Ecology, Federal University of Agriculture, Abeokuta, Nigeria under my supervision.

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DEDICATION

This work is dedicated to Almighty God who with his special grace and favour has gotten this work to a successful end, also dedicated the project work to my parent.

ABSTRACT

The seven key child survival interventions are essential component developed to address the issue of high mortality rate and malnutrition of under five children in Africa. This study was carried out to assess the knowledge, attitude and practices of mothers with children aged 0-36 months on seven key child survival interventions. Using a cross – sectional design the study was conducted in seven primary health carecentres in Abeokuta South and Odeda local government area. A total of 300 motherswere selected by simple random sampling technique. Information on socio-economics and demographics characteristics were collected with the aid of semi-structured questionnaire, while knowledge was assessed using twenty six point scale questions and eighteen point scale questions was used to assess practices. Five point likertscale was used to assess the attitude of the respondents using twenty four attitudinal questions. The knowledge and practices was ranked good, moderate and poor also the attitude was categorized into positive and negative. Data was analyzed with Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 20.0 using descriptive(frequency, Mean and Standard deviation) and inferential statistics (Chi-square).Result indicates that majority (95.7%) of the respondents were Yoruba, also there were more Christians (68.7%) than other religions while most (75.3%) of the children were between the age range of 0-6 months. About (40%) of the respondents had good knowledge, 56% had moderate knowledge and 4.3% had poor knowledge of seven key child survival interventions, whereas 32% had good practices, 56.7% had moderate practices and 11.3% had poor practices of seven key child survival interventions.Majority of the respondent (81%) had positive attitude towards given water to baby less than six months also 73.7% had positive attitude towards babies not given immunization at birth and 84%had positive attitude toward withdrawing breastmilk from children with diarrhea. The prevalence of malnutrition among the childrenwere, wasting

(11.7%), stunting (22.4%) and underweight (14.7%) also there was a significant association between knowledge and practices of mothers($p= 0.000$).Underweight among children had significant association with malaria treatment with insecticide treated net ($p=0.003$) and using oral rehydration therapy to treat diarrhea ($p=0.042$).Practices of mothers on these interventions are low compare to the level of their knowledge and they have negative attitude towards the seven key child survival intervention. Health workers should place more emphasis on helping the mothers in raising their critical consciousness, also reorient the mothers on benefits and their wrong attitude toward these interventions which may affect the nutritional status of their children.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

My profound gratitude goes to Almighty God who has given me the opportunity to be alive and witness this moment. I grateful to my supervisor Dr. W.A.O Afolabi for his encouragement, undivided guidance, supervision, insight, patience and encouragement throughout the course of this project.

My warmest appreciation goes to my parents Mr. and Mrs. Mayakifor their financial support advice and prayers throughout the course of my study. I am also greatly indebted to my family member, Mr and MrsTaiwo, AnutyYejide, MrsOlabisiOshodi-Sunmola and the contribution during my course study, for their support and advise.

Lots of thanks to my lecturerProf. (Mrs.) I.O Olayiwola, Dr. W.A.O Afolabi, Dr. (Mrs.) S.A Sanni, Dr. O.O Onabanjo, Dr. C.A Oladoyinbo, Mrs. O.O Akinbule and Mrs. O.O Bolajoko, of the department of Nutrition and Dietetics.Thank you all for the knowledge impacted on me. God bless you abundantly.

And to all my friends and colleagues,OyeyemiOyedeji, LawalSeun, OjoModupe,AwololaTunde to mention few. I thank you so much for your support, encouragement and unfailing interest in my study. May we all meet at the top.

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CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

All children have a guaranteed right to survival. Child survival is not only of global concern but it is of concern in all cultures, races, religion, tribes and peoples (WHO 2006). Thus, at the 1990 World Summit for Children, World leaders, in their Plan of Action identified the following specific actions for child survival, protection and development-the Convention on the Rights of the Child, Child health, Food and nutrition, Role of women, maternal health and family planning, Role of the family, Basic education and literacy, Children especially in difficult circumstances. (Martines *et al.*, 2005). Under five children form a large age group which are mostly vulnerable to infectious diseases like diarrhea, respiratory tract infection, food borne illness and state of undernutrition enhances the chance of developing these diseases resulting into high morbidity and mortality (Ramani, 2010).

The high mortality among children tends to be a global public health problem and a threat to child survival, especially in developing countries, including Nigeria. Child survival in Nigeria is threatened by nutritional deficiencies and other curable and preventable illnesses particularly malaria, diarrheal diseases, acute respiratory infections and vaccine preventable diseases which account for the majority of morbidity and mortality in childhood (Policy Project/Nigeria, 2002). Traditionally, most of the control measures to reduce incidence of these diseases has been multiple diseases-specific control programmes which have been found to have had administrative, political and technical difficulties in the delivery of health services (Steinwand, 2001).

Child survival strategy is an essential component of public health which was developed by World Health Organization (WHO), United Nations Children's Fund (UNICEF) and World Bank in 2006 to address the issue of high mortality rate of under-five in African region. The

strategy aims to scale up a defined set of effective child survival interventions, including antenatal care, newborn care, appropriate infant feeding, immunization, management of common childhood illnesses and use of insecticide treated nets (ITNs) (Habimana *et al.*, 2010). Intervention is a biologic agent or action intended to reduce morbidity or mortality. It is targeted usually at direct causes of mortality or malnutrition, it's not often targeted at underlying determinants of health but increasingly this need is being recognized. Example of these intervention are, insecticide treated bednets to prevent malaria, vitamin A supplementation, measles vaccination, access to clean water and sanitation, treatment with Oral rehydration therapy for diarrhea (Jones *et al.*, 2003). Child survival interventions aim to achieve improvements on a large scale and to sustain these over time. Their ultimate goal is to bring about shifts in social norms. This requires the direct involvement of communities at many levels.

WHO and UNICEF (1998) identified twelve, family and community practices (FCPs) considered being of key importance in order to ensure survival, reduce morbidity and promote healthy growth and development among young children. Eleven of these practices relate to the provision of good home care for the child while the twelfth practice ensures that the mother receives adequate antenatal care to enable a newborn child get the best start in life. The WHO and UNICEF advanced FCPs to include presenting children as scheduled to complete a full course of immunizations, Bacillus Calmette-Guerin (BCG), Diphtheria, pertussis (whooping cough) and tetanus (DPT) , PENTAVELENT, Oral polio vaccine (OPV), and Measles vaccines, before their first birthday, breastfeeding infants exclusively for six months, starting at six months of age to feed children with freshly prepared energy and nutrient rich complementary foods, while continuing to breastfeed up to two years or longer, ensuring that children received adequate amount of micronutrients (vitamin A, iron and zinc in particular) either in their diet or through supplementation, disposing faeces safely and

washing hands after defecation before preparing meals and before feeding children and protecting children in malaria endemic areas, by ensuring that they sleep under insecticide treated bed nets. Other needed are continue feeding and offering more fluids including breast milk to children when they are sick, giving sick children appropriate home treatment for infections, recognizing when sick children need treatment outside the home and seeking care from appropriate providers, following the health worker's advice about treatment, follow-up and referral, promoting mental and social development by responding to a child's needs for care, and through talking, playing and providing a stimulating environment, and ensuring that every pregnant woman has antenatal care.

Poor maternal, newborn and child health remains a significant problem in developing countries. In 2003, the Bellagio Lancet Child Survival Series helped to raise global awareness that each year over 10 million children under five die in the world, mainly from preventable conditions that rarely kill children in rich countries (Black *et al.*, 2003). The second Lancet series focused on a previously neglected subset of child deaths, almost 40% of all under-five deaths which occur among newborn babies (Lawn *et al.*, 2004). Together, these two series provided the necessary evidence to revitalise efforts to reduce child and newborn deaths and to achieve Millennium Development Goal 4. Both series demonstrated that the majority of child deaths could be prevented with simple, low-cost interventions feasible now, yet not reaching poor children. A child's health during the first five years of life is largely set by events occurring during the prenatal, intranatal and post-neonatal periods (Darmstadt *et al.*, 2005). The first year of life is the most dangerous as children are most likely to die at this time more than at any other period of their lives. Adequate nutrition and health care during the first few years of life is fundamental for child survival and prevention of malnutrition (Atimo and Oyewole 2008). It is important to know that it is during infancy and early childhood that irreversible faltering in linear growth and cognitive deficit occurs (Engberg-pederson, 2007).

Strategy for improving child health and development will not be effective unless it addresses the behaviour of families and communities following from the assertion. It can be noted that families and communities have the responsibility to take decisions and actions that will improve their children's survival, growth and development. Such decisions and actions include exclusive breastfeeding for six months, proper hygiene practices, using insecticide treated bed nets to prevent malaria, among others. Thus any attempt to promote childcare practices need to be done within the family and community (Lambrechts *et al.*, 1999)

1.1 Problem Statement

Despite substantial progress in reducing global child mortality over the past two decades, only 13 of 61 countries with high under-five mortality rates are currently able to meet the fourth Millennium Development Goal: A two third reduction in under-five child mortality by 2015 (Wang *et al.*, 2011). Progress on child mortality and undernutrition has seen widening inequities and a concentration of child deaths and undernutrition in the most deprived communities, threatening the achievement of the Millennium Development Goals (Carlos *et al.*, 2012). The leading contributors to child death are diarrhea disease, pneumonia, malaria, and neonatal illness all diseases with well validated and low-cost prevention methods and treatments (Bhutta *et al.*, 2005). Yet these interventions are not reaching those who most need them (UNICEF 2013).

Delayed access to effective care to children increased under-five mortality from malaria, neonatal asphyxia, acute respiratory infection, and diarrheal disease (Reyes *et al.*, 1997). The wellbeing of a child is dependent on the mother to a very large extent. The knowledge of the mother is therefore a pre-requisite to the practices of good and healthy life. Mothers lack the knowledge or understanding towards the seven keys child survival and it has been observed that improper compliance, practice and awareness could lead to high mortality and morbidity rate among children. Despite these gains, child survival remains an urgent concern. The toll of

under-five deaths over the past two decades is staggering: between 1990 and 2013, 223 million children worldwide died before their fifth birthday (Ramani, 2010).

Hence the need to assess the knowledge, attitude and practices of seven key survival interventions among mothers in selected primary health care center in Abeokuta south and Odeda local government area in Nigeria as a case study.

1.2 Justification

Children's health status is an important population marker of environmental threats to human health. Child survival intervention has an alleged impact on reducing maternal, neonatal and child mortality. The under-five mortality rate is a key indicator of child well-being, including health and nutrition status. Up to two-thirds of these deaths can be prevented if mothers and newborns receive known, effective interventions (Darmstadt *et al.*, 2005). It as being observe that mothers do not adpot behaviour that will prevent mortality during infant and childhood health problems before the children grow up. Such behaviour as children not being propely cared for at home when they are sick, poor care-seeking practices, poor hygiene practices and inappropraite feeding practices. (Sanghvi and Murray, 1997). Studies have shown that home-based newborn care interventions can prevent 30–60% of newborn deaths in high mortality settings under controlled conditions (Bang *et al.*, 1999).

Educating mothers on the importance of seven key survival interventions is likely to be effective if we know the characteristics of the mothers in terms of knowledge, their attitude and practices about seven key child survival interventions.

1.3 Broad Objective

To assess the knowledge, attitude and practice of mothers on seven key child survival interventions in Abeokuta South and Odeda Local Government, primary health care centre.

1.4 Specific Objectives

- I. To assess the social-economic and demographic characteristics of mothers
- II. To determine the level of awareness of seven key child survival intervention
- III. To assess the knowledge, attitude and practices of mother's regarding the seven key child survival intervention
- IV. To assess the nutritional status of their children
- V. To establish association between knowledge, attitude and practice of seven key child survival intervention and nutritional status of children between 0-36months

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Child Mortality

Nigeria's estimated population of 120 million in 2004 (National Population Commission, 2004) makes it the largest country in sub-Saharan Africa and the tenth most populated country worldwide. Nigeria's population is largely rural, with 63.7 percent of the population living in rural areas. Currently, about 45 percent of Nigeria's total population is less than age 15, with about 20 percent (24 million) under age five.

Child mortality is a sensitive indicator of a country's development and telling evidence of its priorities and values (Park, 2002). Every day, more than 26,000 children under the age of five die around the world, mostly from preventable causes (Black *et al.*, 2003). Nearly all of them live in the developing countries (Black *et al.*, 2003). More than one third of these children die during the first month of life, usually at home and without access to essential health services and basic commodities that might save their lives. Some children succumb to respiratory or diarrhea infections that are no longer threats in industrialized countries or to early childhood diseases that are easily prevented through vaccines, such as measles. In up to half of under-five deaths an underlying cause is under nutrition, which deprives a young child's body and mind of the nutrients needed for growth and development (Bryce *et al.*, 2005). Unsafe drinking water, poor sanitation and inadequate hygiene also contribute immensely to child mortality and morbidity (Bryce *et al.*, 2005).

The highest maternal, neonatal and under-five mortality rates are in sub-Saharan Africa and in Southern Asia. It has also been observed that every year, more than 10 million children die before they reach their fifth birthdays in low- and middle-income. Most of these deaths are as a result of lack of effective interventions that would combat common and preventable childhood illnesses (Lee, 2003).

Poor maternal and child health indicators have been a recurring public health challenge in Nigeria since documentation of national Maternal, Newborn, and Child Health (MNCH) statistics began in the early 1990s (National population commission, 2009). To address this problem, many interventions were instituted to ensure that Nigeria achieves the relevant Millennium Development Goals (MDGs). Nevertheless, various intervention reports have documented mixed findings of the successes and challenges as well as threats to the attainment of MDGs 4 and 5 (child and maternal mortality reduction, respectively) in Nigeria (Findley *et al.*, 2015).

The under-five mortality rate has declined by almost half since 1990, dropping from 90 to 46 deaths per 1,000 live births in 2013. The absolute number of under-five deaths was cut in half during the same period, from 12.7 million to 6.3 million, saving 17,000 lives every day (UNICEF, 2014). Under-five mortality is also falling among the poorest children in all regions. Moreover, greater absolute declines have been achieved among the poorest households than among the richest in all regions. Between 1990 and 2010, the gap between the richest and poorest households narrowed in all regions except sub-Saharan Africa. However, substantial disparities remain in all regions (UNICEF, 2014). Despite these advances, the toll of under-five deaths over the past two decades is staggering: between 1990 and 2013, two hundred and twenty three million children worldwide died before their fifth birthday (UNICEF, 2014).

Childhood deaths have been reported to be concentrated in poor resource settings like Nigeria where poverty, ignorance and social instability have provided a platform on which malnutrition and infection-related diseases have resulted in childhood deaths (Lee, 2003). Impressive progress has been made in improving the survival rates and health of children, even in some of the poorest countries, since 1990 (Murray *et al.*, 2007). However it is

worrisome to note that high rate of infant and child morbidity and mortality is still one of the greatest challenges facing most of the countries in Sub-Saharan Africa (Park, 2002).

2.2 Definition of Terms

Child

Every human being below the age of eighteen years unless under the law applicable to the child, majority is attained earlier (CONCERN Worldwide, 2012).

Survival

The fact or act of surviving; continued existence or life (CONCERN worldwide, 2012).

Child survival

All children have the right to life and governments are expected to protect this right, but the term child survival refers to the survival of children aged 0-5 years, commonly called “Under-fives” (Alice, 2012). The Concentrated efforts by governments, the United Nations, organizations, and communities to use effective, low-cost solutions to protect children from illness during their first five years of life (CONCERN Worldwide, 2012).

Mortality: The death rate of a population.

Morbidity: The incidence of disease, as a rate of a population which is affected.

These are the Following Indicators of Child Mortality;

Under Five Mortality Rated (U5MR): Also called child mortality rate is the probability of a child dying between birth and exactly 5 years as express per 1000 live births.

Infant MortalityRate (IMR): Probability of dying between birth and exactly one year as expressed per 1000 live births.

Neonatal Mortality Rate (NMR): Probability of dying between birth and exactly 28 days as expressed per 1000 livebirths (Donna and Chris, 2013)

2.3 Threats to Child Survival

According to USAID (2012), major killers of children globally which were identified are chiefly;

1. New-born infections and birth complications
2. Pneumonia and acute respiratory infections
3. Diarrheal diseases
4. Malaria
5. Measles
6. Under-nutrition

The biggest threats to child survival in developing countries are;

Neonatal Causes

Nearly four million babies die within their first month of life. Babies are extremely vulnerable to infections, especially if their mothers are in poor health.

Pneumonia

A bacteria disease that affects the lungs. Pneumonia causes the deaths of over 1.4 million children each year. Several attempts to understand worldwide child pneumonia mortality have been made over the past 30 years (Bryce, *et al.*, 2005). Despite the difficulties of producing estimates with available evidence, pneumonia has consistently been estimated as the leading single cause of childhood mortality.

Diarrhoea

Unhygienic conditions can cause diarrhoea. This can result in a life-threatening condition of dehydration. Nearly one million children die from diarrhoea each year.

According to UNICEF and WHO (2009), nearly nine million children under five years of age die each year. Diarrhoea is second only to pneumonia as the cause of these deaths.

Diarrhoea disease and its complications remain a major cause of morbidity and mortality in children, especially in developing countries. Diarrhoea is characterised by an increased frequency and volume, and decreased consistency of stool from the norm. Persistent diarrhoea occurs when the duration of symptoms exceeds seven days and chronic diarrhoea when it lasts more than 14 days (Cooke, 2010). Diarrhoea is defined as having loose or watery stools at least three times per day, or more frequently than normal for an individual. Though most episodes of childhood diarrhoea are mild, acute cases can lead to significant fluid loss and dehydration, which may result in death or other

Severe consequences if fluids are not replaced at the first sign of diarrhoea (UNICEF and WHO, 2009). World health organization estimates that 88% of all diarrhoea diseases are due to unsafe water supply, inadequate sanitation and poor hygiene practices (Remidius, 2012). It is the second most common cause of death in children under five years of age worldwide and is responsible for 2.4 million deaths each year (Cooke, 2010).

Malaria

Parasites carried by mosquitoes spread malaria to humans. Every year, an estimated one million people die from malaria, most of whom are children.

Malaria diseases, a preventable and treatable disease has continued to plague under-five children in Nigeria. It accounts for about one million deaths in Africa and 9 out of 10 cases of malaria worldwide occur in Africa, south of the Sahara (Iloh *et al.*, 2013). In Nigeria, malaria accounts for about 11% of maternal deaths, especially for first-time mothers. It

contributes largely to neonatal and perinatal mortality as well as anaemia in young children, thus undermining their growth and development (Ochiawunma *et al.*, 2002). It is estimated that 50% of the population has at least one episode of malaria each year, whereas children less than age five suffer from two to four attacks a year. About 75% of malaria deaths occur in children under five (Ochiawunma *et al.*, 2002). Unhealthy health practices contribute to poor treatment and prevention of malaria infection and invariably cause a rise in family healthcare costs (Iloh *et al.*, 2013).

HIV and AIDS: A mother infected by HIV/AIDS can pass it to her baby through pregnancy, delivery, and breast-milk. Every day, 2,000 infants become infected with HIV.

Malnutrition

A condition caused by not eating enough food or not eating a balanced diet. Malnutrition is the cause of death of six million children each year. Malnutrition is an underlying factor for 53 percent of all deaths of children under five.

(CONCERN World, 2012).

Measles

Measles is an acute viral infection that is often self-limiting. But some children, particularly those who are undernourished or have compromised immune systems, may experience serious side effects, including diarrhoea. Diarrhoea is one of the most common causes of death associated with measles worldwide (UNICEF and WHO, 2009).

2.4 Child survival intervention

Intervention means to reduce child mortality for each of the major direct and underlying causes of death in children younger than 5 years (under-5-deaths). The term intervention is used here in a limited sense to refer to a biological agent or action intended to reduce morbidity or mortality.

Approaches used to reach children and mothers with the interventions they need are referred to as delivery strategies. Interventions include preventive approaches that may reduce the exposure to the infection or condition or reduce the likelihood of exposure that leads to disease and both preventive and treatment approaches to reduce the likelihood that the disease or condition will lead to death.

India and Nigeria account for more than a third of child deaths worldwide. If all women in both countries had completed secondary education, the under-5- mortality rate would have been 61% lower in India and 43% lower in Nigeria, saving 1.35 million children's lives (UNESCO, 2012). Therefore, recognising the relationship between a mother's level of education and infant and childhood mortality, as well as encouraging female education in the broadest sense, seems to be the government's most effective approach for tackling the lingering problems of poor environmental sanitation, inadequate child nutrition, and ignorance of correct child care methods (Ochiawunma *et al.*, 2002).

Although substantial progress has been made towards achieving the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) 4 and 5, the rates of decline in maternal, newborn and under-five mortality remain insufficient to achieve these goals by 2015. Interventions and strategies for improving reproductive, maternal, newborn and child health and survival are closely related and must be provided through a continuum of care approach.

2.5 Key Survival Interventions

Child Survival interventions are those programmes that address the major causes of under-five mortality, especially diarrhoea, acute respiratory infection (ARI) and malaria with an integrated set of interventions related to child health, nutrition, water and sanitation (Alice, 2012). The child survival interventions include:

Preventive interventions of under-five mortality which are;

Exclusive breastfeeding for the first 6 months, continued breastfeeding through the first 2 years of life, use of insecticide-treated nets for malaria, micronutrient supplementation (vitamin A, zinc), complementary feeding, immunization (especially Hepatitis B, measles and tetanus) and neonatal care (clean delivery and new-born temperature management), sanitation (clean water, waste disposal), growth monitoring and promotion, family planning prevention of mother-to-child transmission of HIV in countries with a high prevalence of HIV through administration of an antiretroviral drug.

Therapeutic interventions of greatest impact are;

Oral rehydration therapy for diarrhoea, Antibiotics for neonatal sepsis, pneumonia and dysentery, Anti-malarial drug treatment (UNICEF, 2014).

The child survival interventions that will be focusing on are:

- Early and exclusive breastfeeding 0 – 6 months
- Appropriate complementary feeding 6 – 24 months
- Immunization 0 – 12 months
- Adequate micronutrients through diet and supplementation 6 – 59 months
- Insecticide treated net (ITN)
- Home management of infection
- Oral rehydration therapy (ORT)

2.5.1 Early and Exclusive Breastfeeding

In the Global Strategy for Infant and Young Child, exclusive breast feeding (EBF) for the first 6 months of life, and continued breastfeeding through the second year of life in addition to safe as well as adequate and ageappropriate complementary feeding from 6 to 24 months were

recommended (WHO, 2003). Worldwide, it is estimated that only 34.8% of infants are exclusively breastfed for the first 6 months of life, the majority receiving some other food or fluid in the early months, complementary foods are often introduced too early or too late and are often nutritionally inadequate and unsafe (WHO, 2009). Poor breastfeeding and complementary feeding practices are widespread, particularly in developing countries, leading to early nutritional deficits which are also linked to long-term impairment in growth and health (Magawa, 2012; Ekambaram *et al.*, 2010). In Nigeria, despite the fact that 98% of under five children were ever breastfed at some time, 17% of children below 6 months are breastfed exclusively and complementary foods are introduced early in life while only 10% of children are fed appropriately based on recommended infant and young child feeding practices.

The knowledge and practice of breastfeeding in different communities are greatly influenced by demographic, biophysical, social, cultural and psychological factors. (Thulier and Mercer, 2009).

Early initiation and exclusivity are two important and related parts of establishing the protective effect of breastfeeding against neonatal morbidity and mortality (Tsedeke, 2014). Early breastfeeding is also related to long-term breastfeeding behaviors. Beginning breastfeeding immediately ensures that the newborn receives colostrum, known as liquid gold. Human milk contains at least 100 ingredients not found in formula. Babies are not allergic to the mother's milk, although they may have a reaction to something the mother eats. If she eliminates it from her diet, the problem resolves itself (Ogunrinade, 2013). A history of being breastfed has been associated with decreased risk of acute otitis media, non-specific gastroenteritis, hospitalization for severe lower respiratory tract infections, atopic dermatitis, asthma in young children, obesity, type 1 and 2 diabetes, childhood leukemia, sudden infant death syndrome, and necrotizing enter colitis (Chung *et al.*, 2007).

Breastfeeding is the fundamental component of the child survival strategy. Breast milk is the natural first food for babies. It provides all the energy and nutrients that the infant needs for the first months of life. It continues to provide up to half or more of a child's nutritional needs during the second half of the first year, and up to one third during the second year of life (WHO, 2012).

It has been estimated that 1.3 million deaths could be prevented each year if babies were exclusively breastfed from birth for six months (UNICEF, 2013). The colostrum is of particular nutritional and health value to the infants and it is the infants' first immunization. Colostrum also contains numerous nutrients such as protein, fat, carbohydrates, vitamins and minerals (Davis *et al.*, 1999). Exclusive breastfeeding also provides health benefits for mothers (Alive and Thrive, 2012).

In developing countries, the lives of one million infants can be saved just by promoting breastfeeding. In addition to the nutritional and psychological values of breast milk, it contains antibodies that help to protect the baby against many common childhood diseases. It is clean, always at the right temperature, inexpensive and nearly every mother has more than enough of this high quality food for her baby. Breastfeeding is the ideal method suited for the physiological and psychological needs of an infant (Subbiah, 2003).

The WHO recommends that all mothers should breastfeed their babies exclusively for 6 months with supplemental breast feeding continuing up to the second year of life or later. Exclusive breastfeeding for the first 6 months of life improves the growth, health and survival status of newborns and is one of the most natural and best forms of preventive medicine (Hoddinott *et al.*, 2008).

Optimal infant and young child feeding (IYCF) practices are fundamental in ensuring appropriate growth and development, and ultimately the survival of infants and young children (Bhutta *et al.*, 2005; Black *et al.*, 2003).

Interventions that seek to increase exclusive breastfeeding should consider focusing on women who are most at risk of early discontinuation of breastfeeding. Nevertheless, some working mothers may find it difficult to follow this recommendation. Hence, it is important to explore the proportion of working mothers who decide to not exclusively breastfeed and the reasons behind their decision.

2.5.2 Appropriate Complementary feeding

The period of complementary feeding refers to the stage of life when foods and/or liquid milks are fed to infants and young children in addition to breast milk; non-breast-milk food items consumed at this time are defined as complementary foods (UNICEF and WHO, 2006)

Complementary feeding studies have shown that feeding with appropriate, adequate and safe complementary foods from the age of 6 months onwards leads to better health and growth outcomes. Poor breastfeeding and complementary feeding practices have been widely documented in the developing countries. Only about 39% of infants in the developing countries, 25% in Africa are exclusively breastfed for the first six months. Additionally, 6% of infants in developing countries are never breastfed. (Kimani-Murage, *et al.*, 2011).

Malnutrition is responsible, directly or indirectly, for over half of all childhood deaths. Infants and young children are at increased risk of malnutrition from six months of age onwards, when breast milk alone is no longer sufficient to meet all nutritional requirements and complementary feeding needs to be started. Malnutrition has been shown to account for 60% of the 10.9 million deaths annually among children under five. Well over two-thirds of these deaths,

which are often associated with inappropriate feeding practices, occurring during the first year of life.

The problem of poor quality of complementary food has been underemphasized in nutrition programming for quite some time. (Dewey and Kathryn, 2005)

Key principles guide programming for complementary feeding. (Pan American Health Organization/World Health Organization, 2012). They includes:

- Educating and improving caregiver practices
- Increasing energy density and/ or nutrient bioavailability of complementary foods;
- Providing complementary foods, with or without added micronutrients
- Fortifying complementary foods, either centrally or through home fortification including use of multiple micronutrient powder (MNP), in each case paying greater attention to food insecure populations.

The complementary feeding period generally from 6-24 months is a particularly vulnerable period in the lives of children. It is the peak period for growth faltering, deficiency of certain micronutrient and high prevalence of some childhood illness like diarrhoea and respiratory infection. Malnutrition from inadequate breastfeeding and poor complementary feeding practices is a particular risk in this age group of children in resource-poor countries of sub-Saharan Africa and contributes significantly to high child mortalities in this region. (WHO, 1998).

2.5.3 Insecticide treated net

Malaria is of important public health concern in Nigeria especially because of its impact on child and maternal health (Orimadegun *et al.*, 2007). Malaria control still remains a challenge in Africa where 45 countries, including Nigeria, are endemic for malaria, and about 588

million people at risk (WHO, 2008). Children under five are vulnerable to severe attacks of malaria because of their lack of immunity.

The Roll Back Malaria (RBM) programme was initiated in 1998 by the World Health Organisation (WHO) to make available a number of key evidence-based and cost-effective malaria control interventions that include home management of malaria (HMM) with emphasis on early and appropriate treatment of malaria particularly for children under five years old (Attaran *et al.*, 2004). The RBM target through HMM was to ensure at least 60% and 80% of mothers of children under five years have access to information on HMM and affordable anti-malaria's for effective malaria treatment by 2005 and 2010 respectively in order to achieve the goal to halve malaria morbidity and mortality worldwide by 2010 and further reduce the burden by 50% in 2015 (Abasiattai, *et al.*, 2009). This is expected to contribute to attaining the Millennium Development Goal (MDG) of halting malaria and beginning to reverse the incidence of malaria and other major diseases by the target date of 2015 (UN, 2000).

The use of insecticide treated nets has been advocated for the prevention of the vector borne transmitted disease (malaria) by the World Health Organisation and UNICEF for more than a decade now through the roll back malaria (RBM) programme.

These nets have also been shown to reduce the severity and mortality due to malaria in endemic regions as well as all-cause mortality by approximately 20%. The use of insecticide treated nets (ITNs) and anti-malarial drugs are essential and can reduce the incidence of malaria in children (Ogunjimi *et al.*, 2012). Although the cost of insecticide-treated mosquito nets are minimal, only eight percent of children under five in Sub-Saharan Africa sleep under treated nets and only one in three children are treated with anti- malarial drugs (Ogunjimi *et al.*, 2012).

2.5.3.1 Effectiveness of insecticide treated nets

ITNs are estimated to be the twice as effective as untreated net and offer greater than 70% protection as compared with no net (Bachon *et al.*, 2006). These nets are dip-treated using a synthetic parathyroid insecticide such as deltamethrin or permethrin which will double the protection over a non-treated net by killing and repelling mosquitoes. To obtain maximum effectiveness, ITNs are re-impregnated with insecticide every six months.

The distribution of mosquito nets impregnated with insecticide has been shown to be extremely effective method of malaria prevention and it is also one of the most cost effective methods of prevention. Use of Insecticides Treated bed nets is part of World Health Organizations' Millennium Development Goals (WHO, 2012).

Insecticide Treated Nets protects people sleeping under it and simultaneously kills mosquitoes that contact the net. Some protection is provided to others by this method, including people sleeping in the same room but not under the net. However, disease transmission may be exacerbated after the bed nets have lost their insecticide properties under certain circumstance. Although, Insecticides treated nets are still protected by physical barrier of the netting, non-users could experience an increased rate of bites as mosquitoes are deflected away from the non-lethal bed-nets users. (Yakob *et al.*, 2009). ITNs protect the individuals or households that use it and also protect people in the surrounding community in one of two ways (Maxwell et al, 2002).

- ITNs kills' adult mosquitoes infected with malaria parasite directly which increases their mortality rate and can therefore decrease the frequency in which persons in the community are bitten by an infected anopheles mosquito (Killeen and Smith, 2007).
- Certain, malaria parasites require days to develop in the salivary glands of the vector (mosquito). Plasmodium falciparum for example the parasite that is responsible for

the majority of death due to malaria infections, takes 8 days to mature and therefore malaria transmission to humans does not place until approximately the 10th day, although it would require blood meals at intervals of 2-5days (Smith and Mcknzie, 2004). By killing the mosquitoes before maturation of the malaria parasite, ITNs can reduce the number of encounters of infected mosquito with humans (Killeen and Smith, 2007).

In recent times in Nigeria, tens of millions of insecticide treated nets have been distributed under the highly celebrated Roll Back Malaria programme of the Federal Ministry Of Health in partnership with local and international Aids and donor agencies, political groups, NGOs and civil society organizations, While these efforts are laudable, the concept of community education on the safe handling of these nets remains unattended to. People are ignorant of how to make efficient and effective use of Insecticide Treated Nets.

2.5.4 Adequate micronutrients through diet and supplementation

Micronutrient deficiencies, including deficiencies of vitamin A, iron, iodine, zinc and folic acid, are common among women and children in low- and middle-income countries. Ensuring adequate micronutrient status in women of reproductive age, pregnant women and children improves the health of expectant mothers, the growth and development of unborn children, and the survival and physical and mental development of children up to 5 years old.

Micronutrient malnutrition is a serious childhood dietary problem in developing nations. Deficiencies in vitamins A and B12, iron, folic acid and zinc, are preventable causes of poor childhood growth and school performance. Micronutrients are nutrients needed in minute specific quantities in the body. Most of them are not generated in the body but are derived from food intake.

Micronutrient deficiency is associated with an impairment of immune responses and increased susceptibility to infections like upper and lower respiratory tract infections (URI/LRI) and skin infections especially in children (West *et al.*, 2000).

Programmes to address micronutrient deficiencies include delivery of supplements to specific vulnerable groups, home fortification of complementary food for children aged 6 to 23 months and fortification of staple foods and condiments.

2.5.4.1 Iron deficiency anaemia (IDA)

To combat the micronutrient deficiencies especially IDA several intervention programmes have been initiated. The most commonly adopted strategy is the dietary supplementation could be an effective, preventive and curative strategy, in contrast to dietary diversification and food fortification, in providing immediate relief.

2.5.4.2 Vitamin A Deficiency (VAD)

Vitamin A supplementation is one of the effective strategies to prevent Vitamin A deficiency among under-five children. Public health sectors are actively participating in implementation of this National Health programme, whereas majority of under-five mothers are not aware of this scheme.

Supplements given two to three times per year can prevent blindness and lower the risk for death from diarrhoea, malaria and measles. These capsules are inexpensive, yet 28% of children in poor countries are not receiving this treatment (Ogunjimi *et al.*, 2012). Coverage of vitamin A supplementation, often combined with immunization campaigns during Child Health Days, remained high (70 per cent) in all programme countries. UNICEF has been instrumental in promoting the integration of vitamin A supplementation with routine health

service delivery, supporting several countries with national planning. As a result, 63 countries have implemented vitamin A supplementation as part of their national health programmes.

Vitamin A (retinol) is an essential, fat soluble nutrient stored in body organs, mainly the liver. It is released, as needed, into the bloodstream, becoming available for use by cells throughout the body. Vitamin A is an essential nutrient for maintaining eye health and vision, growth, immune function and survival. Everybody needs Vitamin A to protect and promote their health, but it is especially critical for growing infants and children.

2.5.4.3 Zinc

Adequate zinc intake among children is critical for normal growth and development. Recent supplementation trials have shown that adequate zinc leads to a substantial reduction in childhood diarrhoea cases (WHO, 2009).

2.5.5 Immunization

Childhood immunization has been a great concern of the World Health Organization and the organization rates immunization as one of the interventions with a large potential impact on health outcome (WHO, 2000) as diseases have occurred whenever children remain unimmunized or under immunized. While advanced nations have achieved reduction in morbidity and mortality rates from communicable diseases through effective immunization programmes, infectious diseases remain a major contributory factor to the high infant and child morbidity and mortality rates in developing countries (Baqui *et al.*, 1993).

Immunization is one of the most successful and cost-effective public health interventions. In 2010, global efforts to immunize children with vaccines against life-threatening diseases set a record high, reaching 109 million children and averting more than two million deaths along with countless episodes of illness and disability annually (UNICEF, 2013).

The two most effective means of preventing diseases, disability and death from infectious diseases have been sanitation and immunization (Walter *et al.*, 1995). The Expanded Programme on Immunization (EPI) was established to fight against six vaccine preventable diseases which are measles, diphtheria, tuberculosis, poliomyelitis, tetanus and pertussis (EPI, 1998). The program aims at reducing morbidity and mortality associated with not immunizing the children. An important aspect of the exercise was to ensure that every contact a child has with the health facility, should be utilized as an opportunity for vaccination (Ajayi, 2004).

According to UNICEF and WHO guidelines, a child should receive a BCG vaccination to protect against tuberculosis, three doses of DPT to protect against diphtheria, pertussis, and tetanus, three doses of oral polio vaccine (OPV), and a measles vaccination-all by the age of 12 months. Immunizing children against vaccines-preventable diseases before the first year of life is life-saving. Despite significant progress in immunizing children, a significant percentage of children still do not receive the complete regimen of vaccinations for their first year. Globally, twenty four million children - almost 20% of all children born in 2007 did not receive the complete regimen of vaccinations for their first year (Ogunjimi *et al.*, 2012).

Vaccines work by introducing into a person's immune system a harmless form of bacterium, toxin or virus that a healthy person's body recognizes as unusual and responds by devising a defence (immunity) against it (Oladipo and Ejembi, 2013). In some countries currently, pneumococcal and rotavirus vaccines are now available and prevent the leading cause of the two main child killers, namely; pneumonia and diarrhea (Ogunjimi *et al.*, 2012).

2.5.5.1 Concern of Mothers on Immunization for their Children

Vaccines are generally quite safe. The protections they provide far outweigh the risk of serious problems from them. Still, some parents are reluctant to immunize their children due to fear of side effects (Yarwood *et al.*, 2005). Some consider it to be a threat to their

children's lives as they themselves claimed not to have been immunized during childhood. Some even bluntly refuse immunization because of religious beliefs (Streefland *et al.*, 1999). Some studies attributed acceptability of immunization to the kind of relationship that exists between the vaccinators and mothers, stressing on the attitude of the health care providers when being approached by mothers for their children vaccination (Streefland *et al.*, 1999). Unfortunately, some children miss vaccination opportunity as a result of the parents' misperception on the competence of some of the vaccinators (Streefland *et al.*, 1999; Nichter, 1990). The most common reasons for incomplete immunization were inadequate vaccine supply in health facilities (Babalola 2011). The reasons mothers gave are lack of knowledge about immunization benefits, routine immunization schedule and the required number of doses. Some women believed that their children were too young to receive specific vaccines, particularly those involving the use of needles and syringes also some women gave reasons related to mother's unavailability, including sickness, travel time and time constraints (Babalola 2011).

2.5.6 Oral rehydration therapy

According to UNICEF and WHO (2009), Oral rehydration therapy (ORT) is heralded as one of the most important medical advances of the 20th century and is the cornerstone of fluid replacement. In a healthy child, the small intestines absorb water and electrolytes from the digestive tract so that nutrient - rich fluids may be transported to other parts of the body through the bloodstream. In a sick child, diarrhoea causing pathogens damage the intestines causing an excessive amount of water and electrolytes to be secreted rather than being absorbed. When the ORS solution reaches the small intestines, the sodium and glucose in the mixture are transported together across the lining of the intestines, and the sodium, which is now in higher concentrations in the intestines, promotes water absorption back into the body from the gut (UNICEF and WHO, 2009).

Oral Rehydration Salt (ORS) therapy is one of the recognized evidence based interventions used to reduce child morbidity and mortality in diarrhea diseases worldwide. Other interventions include breast feeding, complementary feeding, water, sanitation, hygiene, Rotavirus vaccine, Antibiotics, Zinc and Vitamin-A. Availability of ORS at community level has been shown to reduce diarrhea related mortality among under-five children. Combining ORS with other interventions has also been shown to significantly increase the extent of reduction in diarrhea related morbidity (Swetha *et al*, 2013)

If ORS or other appropriate fluids are not available, increased amounts of almost any fluid could also help to prevent dehydration. Continuing to feed the child during the diarrhoea episode, while providing oral rehydration therapy, further supports the absorption of fluids from the gut into the blood- stream to prevent dehydration. Children receiving food during the diarrhoea episode are also more likely to maintain their nutritional status and their ability to fight infection (UNICEF and WHO, 2009).

2.5.6.1 Control of Diarrhoea Diseases (CDD) Program

The Control of Diarrhoea Diseases (CDD) program started since 1983, in Viet Nam, and up to now this program is implemented routinely in all provinces. The main contents of the program are the promotion of early oral rehydration therapy (ORT) with increased fluids and continued feeding, recommended home fluids and, if necessary, the use of oral rehydration salts solution (ORS) together with good nutrition for children with diarrhoea. This approach has also been included in IMCI, since 1999. Also knowledge and practice of mothers in the family and community had been improved obviously. According to MICS3, there were about 95% children with diarrhoea received one or more of recommended home treatment (receive ORS or other fluids). The priority in the coming years for diarrhoea control are: the use of low osmolarity ORS and zinc supplementation in the management of childhood diarrhea needs to be implemented nationwide; more behavior change communication efforts are required to

keep up good home management practices for diarrhoea and make up for recent drawbacks as well as key practices directly related to childhood diarrhea such as the safe disposal of children's faeces and hand washing; and finally to continue efforts to achieving the MDG goals on water and sanitation. (UNICEF, 2008).

2.5.7 Home management of infection

Not all infections need to be treated by health professionals. Uncomplicated diarrhoea can be successfully managed at home by continuing to feed and administering oral rehydration therapy (ORT) correctly. In malaria's areas, all fevers should be treated at home with antimalarial medications; paracetamol should be given, and the body sponged with tepid water if paracetamol is unavailable (WHO, 1998). Local measles infections (conjunctivitis and mouth ulcers) can also be treated at home. Treating illness at home is a common practice; a review of 24 studies exploring treatments for malaria (McCombie, 1996) reported that levels of self-treatment ranged from 1 – 84%, with 44% of the studies reporting home treatment for more than 50% of episodes. Home treatment is common and it is important to ensure that the behaviours are also appropriate.

Appropriate home treatment involves:

- Early recognition of the illness.
- Prompt and correct procurement and use of relevant treatments.
- The avoidance of ineffective or harmful treatments.
- The continuation of feeding.
- Taking the child to a health facility if he/she does not improve after home treatment.

Interventions to improve home treatment should result in a reduction in severe illness episodes, health service and caregiver burden and pharmaceutical misuse.

2.5.7.1 Home Treatment of Diarrhoea

Diarrhoea diseases are the 3rd leading cause of death in children below 5 years, accounting for 16% of the Nigerian under 5 mortality rate (Federal Ministry of Health Abuja, 2007). Most of these deaths are as a result of severe dehydration, which could have been prevented by oral rehydration therapy (ORT) using Salt Sugar Solution (SSS) or Oral Rehydration Salt (ORS) (Federal Ministry of Health Abuja, 2007). Since 1979 oral rehydration therapy has been the cornerstone of diarrhoea management worldwide with over 150 countries undertaking to attain 80% ORT coverage by 1995 with a view to achieving a reduction of 50% in mortality attributable to diarrhoea by the year 2000. In May 2004, WHO and UNICEF released a joint statement to decrease diarrhoea deaths among the world's most vulnerable children. This statement recommended the use of low osmolality ORS (WHO and UNICEF, 2001) that reduces the need for intravenous fluids, and Zinc supplementation as an adjunct therapy that decreases the duration and severity of the diarrhoea episode and the likelihood of subsequent infection in 2 to 3 months following treatment (WHO and UNICEF, 2001). WHO and UNICEF recommend 20 mg of zinc per day for 10 – 14 days for infants and children, and 10 mg for infants under six months of age, while the low Osmolar ORS is given according to the child's dehydration status and treatment plan (WHO and UNICEF, 2001). Despite the evidence of benefits, there has been little progress on the widespread use of ORS and Zinc for diarrhoea treatment. The situation is even worse in Nigeria where the use of ORT is 38% out of which ORS use is only 34% Nigeria Demographic and Health Survey (2013). With Nigeria's exclusive breast feeding rate at 17%, and with 16% of infants under 2 months of age still being bottle fed, Nigeria Demographic and Health Survey(2013) and bottle feeding being a major risk factor for diarrhoeal diseases, (Curtis *et al.*, 2000) the under 5 aged children in Nigeria may still be in danger of diarrhoea morbidity and mortality.

Problems identified in the preparation and use of ORT at home includes:

- Measuring the correct amount of water and other component
- Adjusting the amount of ORS/RHT for the child's age
- Having time to encourage the child to drink the fluids (especially if the child is vomiting). (Homedes and Ugalde, 2001).

2.6 Women's Knowledge and Practices of Child Survival Strategies

India and Nigeria account for more than a third of child deaths worldwide. If all women in both countries had completed secondary education, the under-5 mortality rate would have been 61% lower in India and 43% lower in Nigeria, saving 1.35 million children's lives (UNESCO, 2013). Women have an enormous impact on their families' welfare (Ogunjimi *et al.*, 2012). Nigeria is second on maternal mortality rate in the world with about 144 girls and women dying every day from complication of pregnancy and child birth. 1 in every 18 women die giving birth compared to 1 in 4800 in the United States (Ogunjimi *et al.*, 2012). Almost two-thirds of the world's 792 million illiterate adults are women (UNESCO, 2012).

The education of girls and women can lead to a wide range of benefits – from improved maternal health, reduced infant mortality and fertility rates to increased prevention against HIV and AIDS. More educated mothers are more likely to know that HIV can be transmitted by breastfeeding, and that the risk of mother-to-child transmission can be reduced by taking drugs during pregnancy and a child born to a mother who can read is 50% more likely to survive past age 5 (UNESCO, 2012). The health of the baby within the mother, the circumstances and events of her birth, her early infancy, childhood, adolescence, early adulthood, her experiences as regards nutrition, child care, education, physical, mental, intellectual and emotional development; all have vital and interdependent roles to play in what we term maternal health (Ogunjimi *et al.*, 2012).

The importance of mother's education for child health and nutrition has been well demonstrated. Maternal education affects children's health and nutritional outcomes through its effect on improving women's socioeconomic status (USAID, 2013). If the mother does not have the knowledge and is not practicing child survival strategies as required, the child will suffer from health problems and growth and development delay (Amanuel *et al.*, 2013). Educated mothers are more likely to ensure that their children receive the best nutrients to help them prevent or fight off ill health, know more about appropriate health and hygiene practices, and have more power in the home to make sure children's nutrition needs are met (UNESCO, 2012). It has been observed that child and maternal mortality have many triggers, both direct and indirect. Poorly funded and culturally inappropriate health and nutrition services, food insecurity, inaccurate feeding practices and lack of hygiene are direct causes of mortality in both children and mothers (UNICEF, 2013). Female illiteracy adversely affects maternal and child survival rates and is also linked to early pregnancy. In many countries, especially where child marriage is prevalent, the lack of primary education and lack of access to healthcare contribute significantly to child and maternal mortality statistics (Ogunjimi *et al.*, 2012). Female illiteracy therefore adversely affects maternal and child survival rates and is also linked to early pregnancy. The lack of primary education and lack of access to health care contribute significantly to child and maternal mortality statistics. Education for the girl child and mothers will reduce the mortality rate of both mother and child. Women who have completed their secondary education are more likely to delay pregnancy, receive prenatal and postnatal care, and have their births attended by qualified medical practitioners. Children born to these women are more likely to receive all the necessary childhood vaccinations, be taken to health care facilities when they are sick and stay healthier than children born to women without formal education (Ogunjimi *et al.*, 2012).

CHAPTER THREE

MATERIALS AND METHODS

3.1 Study Area

The study was conducted in Abeokuta South and Odeda Local Government, area in Ogun state, Nigeria. Ogun State was created 1976 and is in south-western Nigeria. The state was named after the Ogun River which runs right across it from north to west and is strategically located: bordered to the east by Ondo State and to the north by Oyo State and Osun State. Odeda local and Abeokuta South Government Area are part of the twenty local Government areas in Ogun State. The study was carried out in Primary Health Care centers, three were selected in Abeokuta south local government area and four was selected in Odeda local government area of Ogun state, Nigeria.

3.2 Study Design

A cross – sectional and descriptive study design was carried out among mothers with children between 0-36 months attending primary health care centre. Mothers were selected using simple random sampling technique.

3.3 Study location

The study was carried out in selected primary health care centers in Abeokuta south and Odeda local government area, of Ogun State.

3.4 Respondent

Mothers and their children (0-36 months) attending primary health care centre in Abeokuta south and Odeda local Government area, Ogun State.

3.5 Sample Size Determination

The sample size for the study was calculated using the formula

$$N = \frac{Z^2 P (1 - P)}{\epsilon^2} \quad (\text{John, 2003})$$

Where:

n = the minimum desired sample size

z = correspond to 1.96 (at 95% CI)

ϵ = margin of error 5%

P = 22.7% prevalence of measles in Nigeria (NFCNS, 2003)

Therefore

$$N = \frac{1.96^2 \times 0.227 \times 0.773}{0.05^2}$$

$$N = \frac{3.8416 \times 0.175471}{0.0025}$$

$$N = \frac{0.6740893936}{0.0025}$$

N = 269.637 ~ 300 to cater for attrition

N = 300 respondents.

3.6 Sampling Technique

Multi-stage sampling technique was employed in this study. There are nineteen (19) primary health care centers in Abeokuta South local government area, three primary health care center was selected using simple random sampling technique and four primary health care center was selected randomly from twenty nine (29) primary health care centre in Odeda local government area.

3.7 Method of Data Collection

3.7.1 Material for data collection

- Weighting scale
- Infantometer

3.7.2 Instrument for data collection

A semi-structured questionnaire was designed to assess socio-economic, demographic characteristics of the respondents and knowledge point question was asked to assess the respondent on the seven key child survival interventions, also attitudinal questions was asked to assess the attitude of mother on child survival interventions. Practice questions were also

asked from the respondents to assess their practices on child survival intervention. The nutritional status of the children was taken using anthropometric measurements.

3.8 Anthropometric Measurement

Weight of the children was obtained using salter scale/calibrated weighing scale, also the length of the children was taken using infantometer. An index of wasting, stunting and underweight was derived using the WHO (2005) growth standard.

3.9 Knowledge Score

Twenty six point scale questions were asked and score was given to each correct response. Knowledge of mothers on Child Survival intervention was based on correct answers to questions asked. A tally was used to create an index and a score between, (1 – 8) was categorized as poor knowledge, (9 – 17) was categorized as moderated knowledge and (18 – 26) was categorized as Good knowledge.

3.10 Practice Score

Eighteen practices question was asked and scored. Practices of mothers on Child Survival intervention was based on correct practice of child survival intervention. A tally was used to create an index and a score between (1 – 6) was categorized as poor practices, (7– 12) was categorized as moderated practices, and (13 – 18) was categorized as Good practices

3.11 Likert scale

Twenty four attitudinal questions were asked both in positive and negative formed and attitude of mother on child survival intervention was scaled using the five point scale: Strongly Agree, Agree, and Undecided, Disagree and Strongly Disagree. Also the attitude of mothers was categorized into positive and negative based on their responses on the attitudinal questions.

3.12 Data Analysis

WHO Anthro (2005) software was used for analysis of the anthropometry data. Using WHO Z-Score standard of height for age (stunting), weight for age (underweight) and weight for height (wasting) was categorized into Mild malnourished (-1.01 – (-2.00), Moderately malnourished (-2.01 – (-2.00), Severely malnourished(-3.01 – (-9.99), and Normal (-1.00 – (+9.99).

Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 20 was used for statistical analysis. Descriptive statistics such as frequencies, percentages, mean and standard deviation was analysed. Chi-square test was used to find association between variables

CHAPTER FOUR

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Result

Table 1 show the socio-demographic and economic characteristics of the respondent. Majority 95.7% of the mothers were married, 84.3% of the respondents were Yoruba, majority 86.7% of the mothers practices monogamous family. Also, there were more Christians 68.7% than other religions. 42% of the mother has a family size of 4 – 5, also majority 75.3% of the child age range between 0 – 6 months, 21.7% range between 7 – 12 months. More than half 52.7% of the children are female and 47.3% of the children were male. About one third 34.3% of the mothers had tertiary education as the highest level of educational attainment while 8.3% of the mothers had no formal education. More than one-third 38.7% of the women are trader, 7.3% of them were full house wives, 21.7% were artisans, and 19% of the respondents were civil servant. About 7.7% of the mothers earn over a ₦55,000 as monthly income while about 21.7% of the respondents earn less than ₦5,000 as their monthly income and majority of the mothers 36.3% earn between ₦5,001 - ₦25,000.

Table 2 show the knowledge of mothers on seven key child survival interventions, 52.7% of the mother know that breastfeeding should commence within 30 minutes of child birth, 76.3% of the mother know that infant should be exclusive breastfed for 6 months and 6.7% for 4 months, also 54.5% of the mother have the knowledge of give breastmilk only, for a child less than 6 months and 38.8% have the knowledge of given breastmilk with water for a child less than 6 months. 65.3% of the mother has the knowledge of not giving a child less than 6 months other food apart from breast milk and 89.5% has the knowledge that water should be given as other food to a child less than 6 months, 90.3% of the mother know that breastmilk have enough water and nutrient to meet the needs of baby less than 6 months. 82.7% has the knowledge of starting complementary food at age 6 month, and 33.8% know that enrich pap

should be given as complementary foods also 78.3% of the mothers know that, fruits and vegetables should be giving to a child receiving complementary foods and 45.7% has the knowledge of feeding infant 3-5 times during complementary feeding. Majority of the mothers know that baby should be given immunization at birth, only 47.3% know that Bacillus Calmette-Guerin (BCG) is the type of vaccine given at birth, 48.2% know that infant should complete immunization at 12 months and 79.9% know that immunization is does not have adverse effect on the child health. 63.7% of the mother has the knowledge that babies and mothers should sleep under insecticide treated nets and 24.3% for the whole family, majority of the mother know that insecticide treated net can prevent malaria. More than half 53.8% know that Oral rehydration solution can be used to managed diarrhea at home and 5.7% know that given herbs can be used to manage diarrhea at home, 77.3% know that a child with diarrhea should not be withdraw from breastmilk, 48.8% of the mother has the knowledge of removing clothes, sponge with lukewarm water as home magament for babies having fever and majority 92.7% of the mother know that, babies should be giving paracetamol and take the child to hospital as home management of fever and 95% have the knowledge of taking the child to hospital if symptom persist after home management.14.3% of the mother knowledge how to prepare oral rehydration solution and 42.3% know that oral rehydration solution should be discarded after 24 hours of preparation. 45.5% of the mother has the knowledge that vitamin A should be given to babies at age 6 months and 27.1% for vitamin C and majority 95.3% of the mother has the knowledge of a child diet should contain varieties of food including fruits and vegetebles while 4.7% does not have the knowledge.

Table 3 shows the knowledge index of mothers on seven key child survival interventions. It was observed that 56.0% had moderate knowledge, 39.7% of the mothers had good knowledge, while 4.3% of the mothers had poor knowledge on seven child survival interventions. Also the table shows the practices index of mothers on seven key child survival

interventions, it was observed that more than half 56.7% had moderate practices, 32% of the mothers had good practices, while 11.3% of the mothers had poor practices on the seven key child survival interventions.

Table 4 shows the nutritional status of the children. Two third 71.3% of the children had normal nutrition status, 14.3% of the children had moderate wasting, 7.0% of the children had mild wasting, and 4.7% of the children had severe wasting. 56.3% of the children had normal nutritional status, 20.7% of the children had mild stunting 11.7% of the children were severely stunted, while 10.7% of the children were moderately stunted. More than half 58.3% of the children had normal nutritional status, 27.0% of the children had mild underweight, 10.0% of the children had moderate underweight, and 4.7% of the children were severely underweight.

Table 1: Demographic and Socio-economic Characteristics of the Respondents

VARIABLE	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
MATRIAL STATUS		
Single	12	4
Married	287	95.7
Divorce	1	0.3
Total	300	100
ETHNICITY		
Yoruba	253	84.3
Hause	8	2.7
Igbo	22	7.3
Middle Belt	17	5.7
Total	300	100
FAMILY TYPE		
Monogamous	260	86.7
Polygamous	40	13.3
Total	300	100
RELIGION		
Christianity	206	68.7
Muslim	93	31.0
Traditional	1	0.3
Total	300	100
FAMILY SIZE		
1 – 3	115	38.3
4 – 5	126	42.0
6 – 9	55	18.3
10 – 13	4	1.3
Total	300	100
AGE OF CHILD		
0 – 6	226	75.3
7 – 12	65	21.7
13 – 18	6	2
19 – 24	1	0.3
25 – 30	1	0.3
31 – 36	1	0.3
Total	300	100
CHILDREN GENDER		
Male	158	52.7
Female	142	47.3
Total	300	100
HIGHEST LEVEL OF EDUCATION		
No formal Education	25	8.3
Primary Education	60	20.0
Secondary Education	97	32.3
Technical/Vocational education	15	5.0
Tertiary Education	103	34.3
Total	300	100

Demographic and Socio-economic Characteristics the Respondents continue

MOTHERS INCOME PER MONTH		
Less 5000	65	22.1
#5,001 - #15,000	109	37.1
#15,001 - #25,000	48	16.3
#25,001 - #35,000	21	7.1
#35,001 - #45,000	11	3.7
#45,001 - #55,000	17	5.8
>#55,001 and Above	21	7.8
Total	300	100
OCCUPATION		
Full-time housewife	22	7.3
Trader	116	38.7
Artisan	65	21.7
Farmer	17	5.7
Civil servant	66	22
Student	7	2.3
Health personnel	3	0.9
Computer Operator	1	0.3
Bank official	3	1.0
Total	300	100

Table 2: Mothers Knowledge on Seven Key Child Survival Interventions

Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Exclusive Breastfeeding		
When should breastfeeding commence?		
Within 30 minutes after child birth	158	52.7
1 hours after child birth	65	21.7
2 hours after child birth	7	0.7
24 hours after child birth	60	20
3 days	6	2.0
10 days	4	1.4
Total	100	100
How many months should an infant be exclusively breastfed?		
3 months	20	6.7
4 months	20	6.7
5 months	1	0.3
6 months	229	76.3
Above 6 months	30	10
Total	300	100
Water other food should be given to child less than 6 month?		
Breastmilk with water	116	38.8
Breastmilk with herbs	5	1.7
Breastmilk only	163	54.5
Breastmilk with commercial gruel	8	2.7
Breastmilk with pap	4	1.3
Breastmilk and family diet	3	1.0
Total	299	100
Should a child less than 6 months be given other food apart from breastmilk?		
Yes	105	35
No	193	65
Total	300	100
If yes should the child be given?		
Water	94	89.5
Herbal preparation	3	2.9
Glucose	1	1.0
Soft drink	3	2.9
Pap	3	2.9
Supplement	1	1
Total	105	100
Does breastmilk have enough water and nutrients to meet the needs baby less than 6 months?		
Yes	217	90.3
No	29	9.7
Total	300	100

Mothers Knowledge on Seven Key Child Survival Interventions

Appropriate Complementary Feeding		
When should a child be given other foods apart from breastmilk?		
< 4 months	17	5.7
4 – 5 months	20	6.7
At 6 months	248	82.7
7 – 9 months	10	3.3
12 months	5	1.7
Total	300	100
What should be given as complementary foods?		
Watery pap	77	25.8
Commercial gruel	64	21.4
Enrich pap	101	33.8
Family diet	57	19.1
Total	299	100
Complementary foods should be given alongside with?		
Breastmilk	286	95.7
Without breastmilk	13	4.3
Total	299	100
Should a child receiving complementary foods, be given fruits and vegetable?		
Yes	235	78.3
No	65	21.7
Total	300	100
How many times should an infant be fed during complementary feeding?		
Once	29	9.7
2 – 3 times	134	44.7
4 – 5 times	137	45.7
Total	300	100
Insecticide Treated Nets		
Who should sleep under insecticide treated net?		
Mothers	1	0.3
Babies and mothers	191	63.7
Babies alone	35	11.7
Family	73	24.3
Total	300	100
Can malaria be prevented using insecticide treated net?		
Yes	280	93.3
No	20	6.7
Total	300	100

Mothers Knowledge on Seven Key Child Survival Interventions

Immunization		
Should a baby be given immunization at birth?		
Yes	286	95.3
No	14	4.7
Total	300	100
What type of vaccines should be given at birth?		
Measles, Penta 1	22	7.5
BCG, OPV 0, Hep B 0	138	46
Yellow fever, OPV	20	6.7
Tetanus	1	0.3
Don't Know	111	38
Total	292	100
When should an infant complete immunization?		
5 months	1	0.3
9 months	69	23.1
12 months	144	48.2
15 months	21	7
24 months	28	9.4
5 years	5	1.7
Don't know	31	10.4
Total	299	100
How many times should a child be given immunization?		
2 times	12	4
4 times	20	6.7
5 times	46	15.5
6 times	124	41.8
9 times	9	3
12 times	1	0.3
Don't know	85	28.6
Total	297	100
Immunization has adverse effect on the child health?		
Yes	60	20.1
No	239	79.9
Total	299	100
Home Management of Infections		
How can diarrhea affecting babies at home be managed?		
By given herbs	17	5.7
By given drugs	86	28.8
By give Oral rehydration solution(ORS)	161	53.7
Breastmilk	10	3.3
Taking the child to the hospital	23	7.7
Oral rehydration solution and breastmilk	2	0.7
Total	299	100

Mothers Knowledge on Seven Key Child Survival Interventions

Should a child with diarrhea be withdrawn from breastmilk?		
Yes	66	22
No	232	77.3
Don't know	2	0.7
Total	300	100
How can we manage fever affecting babies at home?		
Remove clothes, sponge with lukewarm water	146	48.8
Bath with cool water	136	45.5
Bath with hot water	13	4.3
Give paracetamol, rub with cool water and give blood tonic	1	0.3
Remove the cloth and open nearby windows	3	1
Total	299	100
A child who has fever at home should be given?		
Paracetamol and taking to hospital	278	92.7
Anti-biotics and treat at home	4	1.3
Malaria drug and treat at home	15	5
Others	3	1
Total	300	100
If symptoms persist after home management what should be done?		
Continue the management	11	3.7
Use traditional management	4	1.3
Take the child to hospital	285	95
Total	300	100
Oral Rehydration Therapy		
How can oral rehydration solution be prepared at home?		
Two 35cl bottles of water, with 1 level teaspoon of salt and 10 cubes of sugar	48	16
One 35cl of bottle of water, with 2 level teaspoon of salt and 5 cubes of sugar	48	16
Two 35cl bottles of water, with 1 level teaspoon of salt and 5 cubes of sugar	43	14.3
One boiled cup of water, 1 spoon of salt and 2 spoon of sugar	7	2.3
One bottle of Eva water and ORS sachet	28	9.3
Half spoon of sugar, 1/2 spoon of salt and 1/2 cup of water	2	0.7
One sachet of pure water with 1 level teaspoon of salt and sugar	3	1
Don't know	121	40.3
Total	300	100
When should ORS be discarded after preparation?		
6 hours	23	7.7
12 hours	31	10.3
24 hours	127	42.3
After 3 days	1	0.3
Don't know	118	39.3
Total	300	100

Mothers Knowledge on Seven Key Child Survival Interventions

Micronutrient Supplementation

The food of a child should contain varieties of food including fruits and vegetables?

Yes	286	95.3
No	14	4.7
Total	300	300

What capsules should be given to babies at age 6 months

Vitamin C	81	27.1
Vitamin A	136	45.5
Vitamin K	3	1
Multi vitamin	3	1
Don't know	76	25.4
Total	299	100

Table 3: Knowledge and Practices of Mothers on Seven Key Child Survival Intervention.

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
KNOWLEDGE		
Poor	13	4.3
Moderate	168	56.0
Good	119	39.7
Total	300	100
PRACTICES		
Poor	34	11.3
Moderate	170	56.7
Good	96	32.0
Total	300	100

Table 4: Nutritional Status of the Children

VARIABLE	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
Weight for height Z score		
Mild (Wasting)	43	14.3
Moderate (Wasting)	21	7.0
Severe (Wasting)	14	4.7
Normal	214	71.3
HEIGHT FOR AGE Z score		
Mild (Stunting)	62	20.7
Moderate (Stunting)	32	10.7
Severe (Stunting)	35	11.7
Normal	169	56.3
WEIGHT FOR AGE Z score		
Mild (Underweight)	81	27.0
Moderate (Underweight)	30	10.0
Severe (Underweight)	14	4.7
Normal	175	58.3
BMI FOR AGE		
Mild	46	15.8
Moderate	22	7.3
Severe	16	5.3
Normal	214	71.3

Table 5 show the attitude of mothers on seven key child survival intervention, less than half 46% agree that mothers should commence breastfeeding within 30 minutes after child birth, 40% strongly agree, 8.7% disagree, 1.7% strongly disagree and 3.7% were undecided showing positive attitude, having is mean valve >3 . About one third 26.9% disagree that water, herbs and soft drinks should be given to infant less than 6 months, 18.5% strongly disagree, 15.2% agree, 0.6% strongly agree and 1.3% were undecided showing negative attitude, having the mean valve <3 . Whereas 46.3% stongly agree that infant should be exclusively breastfed for 6 month, while 9.7% disagree and 2% were undecided showing positive attitude, having the measn valve >3 , More than one third 47.7% of the respondents strongly agree that breastmilk has enough water and nutrient to meet the needs of babies less than 6 months, 39.3% agree, 11.7% disagree and 0.7% were undecided showing positive attitude, having a mean valve >3 . Half 50% stongly diagree that a child less than 6 months should be given other food apart from breastmilk, 14.3% stongly disagree, 25.3% agree, 3.3% were on undecided showing a negative attitude, having a mean valve <3 . More than half 59.3% of the mother agree that fruits and vegetable should be given to babies receiving complementary foods, 23.3% strongly agree, 11.7% disagree, 1.3% strongly disagree and 4.3 were undecided showing a negative attitude, having a mean valve <3 . More than half 60% of the mothers disagree that breastmilk should not be given to babies alongside with complementary foods, 21.7% stongly disagree, 12.3% agree, 4.3% strongly agree and 1.7% were undecided showing a negative attitude, having a mean valve <3 . More than half 56% agree that babies should be fed with other food apart from breastmilk at 6 months, 32.3% strongly agree, 7.3% disagree, 1.3% strongly disagree and 3.0% were undecided showing a positive attitude, having the mean valve >3 . About 57.5% agree that family diet should be introduced as complementary foods, 17.1% disagree, 14% strongly agree and 10.4 were undecided showing a negative attitude, having a mean valve <3 . About two third 65.9% agree

that infant should be fed up to 3-5 times daily while 22.4% strongly agree, 6.4% disagree, 1% strongly disagree and 4.3% were undecided showing a positive attitude, having the mean value >3 . More than half 68% agree that the diet of a child should contain varieties of food including fruits and vegetable, whereas, 24.7% strongly agree, 3.0% disagree and 3.7% were undecided showing a positive attitude, having the mean value >3 . About half 49.8% agree that at age 6 months vitamin A should be given to infant, 34% strongly agree, 1.7% disagree and 14.7% were undecided showing a negative attitude, having a mean value <3 . The attitude of mothers on babies should not be given immunization at birth, 44% disagree, 29.7% strongly disagree, 12.7% agree, 11% strongly agree and 2.7% were undecided showing a negative attitude, having a mean value <3 . About 46.7% agree that babies should receive immunization 6 times while 22% strongly agree, 5.3% disagree and 23.3% were undecided showing a negative attitude, having a mean value <3 . Less than half 46.7% agree that babies should complete immunization at 12 month, 31.7% strongly agree, 8.7% disagree, 4.7% strongly disagree and 8.3% were undecided showing a negative attitude, having a mean value <3 . More than half 58% strongly agree that insecticide treated nets can prevent malaria, 39.3% agree, 1% disagree and 1% were undecided showing a positive attitude, having a mean value >3 . About 51.2% disagree that babies and mothers should not sleep under insecticide treated nets while 34.1% strongly disagree, 7.4% agree, 6% strongly agree and 1.3% were undecided showing a positive attitude, having a mean value >3 . One third 34.8% agree that water, salt and sugar are the constituent of oral rehydration solution, 31.1% strongly agree, 1.3% disagree, 32.4% were undecided showing a negative attitude, having a mean value <3 . About one third 34.1% agree that oral rehydration solution should be discarded 24 hours after preparation, 27.1% strongly agree, 2.3% disagree, 35.8% were undecided showing a negative attitude, having a mean value <3 . About 44.6% agree that oral rehydration solution should be given to infant as soon as diarrhea starts, 24.5% strongly agree, 4% disagree and 26.5% were

undecided showing a negative attitude, having a mean value <3. More than one third 42.8% agree that diarrhea affecting babies at home can be managed by given oral rehydration solution, 28.4% strongly agree, 1.7% disagree and 26.4% were undecided showing a negative attitude, having a mean value <3. More than one third 43.8% strongly disagree that a child with diarrhea should be withdraw from breastmilk, 40.5% disagree, 8.7% agree, 3.3% strongly agree and 3.7% were undecided showing a positive attitude, having a mean value >3. More than half 52.2% agree that breastmilk and water should be given as cough management at home, 14.4% strongly agree, 9.4% disagree, 3.3% strongly disagree and 20.7% were undecided showing a negative attitude, having a mean value <3. More than half 56.9% disagree that a child with fever at home should be given anti-malaria and not taking to the hospital, 22.7% strongly disagree, 13.7% agree, 4.7% strongly agree and 2.0% were undecided showing a negative attitude, having a mean value <3.

Table 6 shows the positive attitudinal questions, majority 86% had positive attitude toward should commence breastfeeding within 30 minutes after child birth, 10.4% negative attitude, majority 87.6% had positive attitude towards an infant being exclusively breastfed for 6 months whereas 10% had negative attitude. About 87% had positive attitude toward breast milk has enough water and nutrients to meet the needs of babies less than 6 months while 12.4% had negative attitude. More than two third 82.6% had positive attitude towards fruits and vegetable given to babies receiving complementary foods, 13% had negative attitude. 88.3% had positive attitude towards babies been fed with other food apart from breast milk at 6 months whereas 8.6% had negative attitude. 88% had positive attitude towards Infant been fed up to 3-5 times daily 7.3% had negative attitude. Also majority 92.6% had positive attitude toward diet of a child should contain varieties of food including fruits and vegetables while 3.7% have negative attitude. Majority 83.8% had positive attitude towards 6 months infant receiving Vitamin A and 1.7% had negative attitude. 70.7% had positive attitude

towards babies should receive immunization 6 times while 6% had negative attitude. Majority 85% had positive attitude towards babies should complete immunization at 12 months whereas 13.4% had negative attitude. Majority 97.3% had positive attitude towards insecticide treated nets can prevent malaria whereas 13.3% had negative attitude. About 65.7% had positive attitude towards water, salt and sugar are constituent of oral rehydration solution (ORS) while 1.6% had negative attitude. More than half 61% had positive attitude towards oral rehydration solution (ORS) should be discarded 24 hours after preparation while 3% had negative attitude. About two third 68.6% had positive attitude towards oral rehydration solution (ORS) been given to infant as soon as diarrhea starts whereas 4.3% had negative attitude. Two third 71% had positive attitude towards diarrhea affecting babies at home can be managed by given oral rehydration solution (ORS) whereas 2.4% had negative attitude, About 66.3% had positive attitude towards breast milk, warm water with honey should be given as cough management at home whereas 12.6% had negative attitude.

Table 7 shows negative attitudinal questions, majority 81% had positive attitude towards water, herbs and soft drinks should be given to infant less than 6 months while 15.8% had negative attitude. 64.3% had positive attitude towards a child less than 6 months should be given other food apart from breast milk whereas 32.3% had a negative attitude. 81.7% had a positive attitude towards breast milk should not be given to babies alongside with complementary foods while 16.6% had negative attitude. 71% had negative attitude towards family diet should be introduced as complementary foods whereas 18% had a positive attitude. 73.7% had a positive attitude towards babies should not be given immunization at birth while 23.7% had negative attitude. 85% had a positive attitude towards babies and mothers should not sleep under Insecticide treated net whereas 13.3% had a negative attitude. 84% had positive attitude towards a child with diarrhea been withdrawn from breast milk

while 12% had negative attitude. 79.4% had positive attitude towards a child with fever at should be given anti-malaria and not taking to hospital whereas 18.4% had negative attitude.

Table 5: Attitude of Mothers on Seven Key Child Survival Interventions.

Attitudinal Statement	SA	A	UD	D	SD	Σ	σ
Should mothers commence breastfeeding within 30 minutes after child birth?	120(40)	138(46)	11(3.7)	26(8.7)	5(1.7)	3.17	0.926
Water, herbs and soft drinks should be given to infant less than 6 months	3(0.6)	73(15.2)	6(1.3)	129(26.9)	89(18.5)	2.97	0.873
Should an infant be exclusively breastfed for 6 months?	139(46.3)	124(41.3)	6(2.0)	29(9.7)	1(0.3)	3.30	0.817
Does breastmilk have enough water and nutrients to meet the needs of babies less than 6 months?	143(47.7)	118(39.3)	2(0.7)	35(11.7)	2(0.7)	3.33	0.758
A child less than 6 months should be given other food apart from breastmilk?	21(7)	76(25.3)	10(3.3)	150(50)	43(14.3)	2.65	0.926
Should fruits and vegetables be given babies receiving complementary foods?	70(23.3)	178(59.3)	13(4.3)	35(11.7)	4(1.3)	2.94	0.891
Breastmilk shouldn't be given to babies alongside with complementary foods?	13(4.3)	37(12.3)	5(1.7)	180(60)	65(21.7)	2.96	0.815
Babies should be fed with others food apart from breastmilk at 6 months?	97(32.3)	168(56)	9(3)	22(7.3)	4(1.3)	3.13	0.839
Family diet should be introduced as complementary foods?	42(14)	172(57.5)	31(10.4)	172(57.5)	42(14)	1.84	0.862
Infant should be fed up to 3-5 times daily?	67(22.4)	197(65.9)	13(4.3)	19(6.4)	3(1)	3.01	0.849
The diet of a child should contain varieties of food including fruits and vegetables?	74(24.6)	204(68)	11(3.7)	9(3)	2(0.7)	3.09	0.792
At age 6 months, vitamin A should be given to infant?	102(34)	148(49.8)	44(14.7)	5(1.7)	1(0.3)	2.88	1.296
Babies shouldn't be given immunization at birth?	33(11)	38(12.7)	8(2.7)	132(44)	89(29.7)	2.87	1.044
Babies should receive immunization 6 times?	72(24)	140(46.7)	70(23.3)	16(5.3)	2(0.7)	2.47	1.466
Babies should receive immunization at 12 births?	95(31.7)	140(46.7)	25(8.3)	26(8.7)	14(4.7)	2.89	1.154
Insecticide treated net can prevent malaria?	174(58)	118(39.3)	3(1)	3(1)	2(0.7)	3.53	0.656
Babies and mothers shouldn't sleep under insecticide treated net	18(6)	22(7.4)	4(1.3)	153(51.2)	102(34.1)	3.11	0.876
Water, salt and sugar are constituent of oral rehydration solution.	93(31.1)	104(34.8)	97(32.4)	4(1.3)	1(0.3)	2.32	1.674
Oral rehydration solution should be discarded 24 hours after preparation.	81(27.1)	102(34.1)	107(35.8)	7(2.3)	2(0.7)	2.16	1.687
Should oral rehydration solution be given to infant as soon as diarrhoea starts?	73(24.5)	133(44.6)	79(26.5)	12(4)	1(0.3)	2.40	1.528
Diarrhoea affecting babies at home can be managed by given oral rehydration solution.	85(28.4)	128(42.8)	79(26.4)	5(1.7)	2(0.7)	2.46	1.557
A child with diarrhoea should be withdrawn from breastmilk	10(3.3)	26(8.7)	11(3.7)	121(40.5)	26(8.7)	3.17	0.981
Breast milk and warm water with honey should be given as cough management at home	43(14.4)	156(52.2)	68(20.7)	28(9.4)	10(3.3)	2.36	1.355
A child with fever at home should be given anti-malaria and not taking to hospital	14(4.7)	41(13.7)	6(2)	41(13.7)	14(4.7)	2.94	0.855

SD=Strongly Agree, A= Agree, UN= Undecided, D= Disagree, SD= Strongly disagree, σ =standard deviation and Σ = Mean

Table 6: Categorization of Attitude of Mothers on Seven Key Child Survival Intervention

Positive attitudinal questions	Positive attitude (%)	Negative attitude (%)	Undecided (%)
Should mother commence breastfeeding within 30 minutes after child birth?	258(86)	31(10.4)	11(3.7)
Should an infant be exclusively breastfed for 6 months?	263(87.6)	30(10)	6(2.0)
Does breast milk have enough water and nutrients to meet the needs of babies less than 6 months?	261(87)	37(12.4)	2(0.7)
Should fruits and vegetable be given to babies receiving complementary foods?	248(82.6)	39(13)	13(4.3)
Babies should be fed with other food apart from breast milk at 6 months?	265(88.3)	26(8.6)	9(3)
Infant should be fed up 3-5 times daily	264(88)	22(7.3)	13(4.3)
The diet of a child should contain varieties of food including fruits and vegetables?	278(92.6)	11(3.7)	11(3.7)
At Age 6 months, Vitamin A should be given to infant?	250(83.8)	6(1.7)	44(14.7)
Babies should receive immunization 6 times?	212(70.7)	18(6)	70(23.3)
Babies should complete immunization at 12 months?	235(85)	40(13.4)	25(8.3)
INT can prevent malaria	292(97.3)	40(13.3)	4(1.3)
Water salt and sugar are constituent of ORS	197(65.7)	5(1.6)	97(32.3)
ORS should be discarded 24 hours after preparation?	183(61)	9(3)	107(35.7)
Should ORS be given to infant as soon as diarrhea starts?	206(68.6)	13(4.3)	79(26.3)
Diarrhea affecting babies at home can be managed by given ORS	213(71)	7(2.4)	79(26.3)
Breast milk, warm water with honey should be given as cough management at home	199(66.3)	39(12.6)	62(20.7)

Table 7: Categorization of Attitude of Mothers on Seven Key Child Survival Intervention

Negative attitudinal questions	Positive attitude (%)	Negative attitude (%)	Undecided (%)
Water, herbs and soft drinks should be given to infant less than 6 months?	218(81)	76(15.8)	6(1.3)
A child less than 6 months should be given other food apart from breast milk?	193(64.3)	97(32.3)	10(3.3)
Breastmilk shouldn't be given to babies alongside with complementary foods?	245(81.7)	50(16.6)	5(1.7)
Family diet should be introduced as complementary foods?	54(18)	214(71)	31(10.3)
Babies shouldn't be given immunization at birth?	221(73.7)	71(23.7)	8(2.7)
Babies and mothers shouldn't sleep under Insecticide treated net?	255(85)	40(13.3)	4(1.3)
A child with diarrhea should be withdrawn from breast milk	252(84)	36(12)	11(3.7)
A child with fever at should be given anti-malaria and not taking to hospital	238(79.4)	55(18.4)	6(2)

Table 8: show the practices of mothers on seven key child survival interventions 45.5% of the mother introduced breastmilk within 30 minute of child birth, 23.4% introduced breastmilk 1 hour and 24 hours of child birth, 65.3% did not give water, herbs or soft drinks to their child less than 6 months whereas 34.8% give water, herbs and soft drink to their child. Majority 87.3% of mothers breastfed their baby on demand (8-12 times), 7.4% breastfed 4-5 times. More than half 59.2% breastfed for 6 months before the addition of other food, 25.7% above 6 months and 14.7% less than 4 month. Majority 82.6% breastfeed their baby alongside with complementary foods, whereas 17.4% did not breastfeed alongside with complementary foods. 76.7% include varieties of food including fruits and vegetables in their child complementary foods, 69.2% introduced complementary at 6 months, 15.3% less than 4 month, 10.8% 4-5 months. 76% of the mothers fed their baby 2-3 times daily with complementary foods, 11.8% 4-5 times daily and 2% once daily. Majority 85.4% of the receive vitamin A supplement at 6 month whereas 14.6% did not receive vitamin A, 89.9% of the mothers include varieties of food in their child diet while 10.1% did not include varieties in their diet. 98.3% of the mothers take their baby to hospital if symptoms refuse to stop after home management. 29.3% of the mother give paracetamol only to their baby having fever at home, 16.3% bath with cool water as home management of fever, 10% remove cloth and mop their baby body with warm water while 6.3% remove cloth and tepid sponge with lukewarm water. 47.1% give oral rehydration solution as home management of diarrhea, 30% gave drug, 8% gave breastmilk and honey while 4.8% of the mothers take the child to hospital. 66.8% of the mothers give cough drug as home management of cough, 7.3% gave cough drug and take the child to hospital. 57.7% of the mother prepares oral rehydration solution at home, 42.3% did not prepare oral rehydration solution, and 50.5% of the mother discards oral rehydration solution whereas 49.5% did not discard oral rehydration solution. Majority of the mothers and

babies sleep under insecticide treated net and 10.3% did not sleep under insecticide treated net and 91% of the mothers used insecticide treated net to prevent malaria.

Table 9: Show that 94% of the children takes Bacillus Calmette-Guerin (BCG) at birth and 4.8% of the children take Bacillus Calmette-Guerin (BCG) but didn't take it a birth. The study also show that more than half of the children 52.3% complete their vaccine, 39.3% was incomplete, 0.3% did not take vaccines and 8% of the children are not applicable for Diphtheria, pertussis (whooping cough) and tetanus (DPT) , PENTAVELENT and oral polio vaccine (OPV) vaccines. 20.7% of the children complete taking measles vaccine and more two third 79% of the children are not eligible for measles vaccines.

Table 8: Mothers Practices on Seven Key Child Survival Interventions

Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Exclusive Breastfeeding		
In respect to your last child what time did you introduced breastfeeding?		
Within 30 minutes after child birth	136	45.5
1 hour after child birth	70	23.3
3 hours after child birth	1	0.3
6 hours after child birth	6	2
12 hours after child birth	1	0.3
24 hours after child birth	70	23.3
2 days	6	2
3 days	5	1.7
2 weeks after child birth	4	1.3
Total	299	100
Do you give water, herbs and soft drinks to your child less than 6 months?		
Yes	107	35.7
No	192	64.3
Total	299	100
If yes, what do you give?		
Water	102	95.3
Herbs	1	0.9
Soft drinks	4	3.7
Total	107	100
How frequent do you breastfeed your baby?		
On demand (8-12 times)	261	87.3
2 – 3 times	16	5.4
4 – 5 times	22	7.4
Total	299	100
Appropriate Complementary Feeding		
How long do you breastfeed your child before the addition of other food?		
< 4 months	44	14.7
5 months	1	0.3
6 months	177	59.2
Above 6 months	77	25.7
Total	299	100
Do you breastfed your baby alongside with complementary foods?		
Yes	246	82.6
No	52	17.4
Total	298	100

Mothers Practices on Seven Key Child Survival Interventions

Do you include varieties of food including fruits and vegetables in your child complementary foods?		
Yes	227	76.7
No	69	23.3
Total	296	100
In respect to your last child what time did you introduce complementary foods?		
< 4 months	45	15.3
4 – 5 months	32	10.8
At 6 months	204	69.2
7 months	6	2
8 months	1	0.3
12 months	7	2.3
Total	295	100
How frequent do you fed your child with complementary foods per day?		
once	6	2
2 – 3 times	225	76
4 – 5 times	37	12.5
6 – 7 times	13	4.4
8 – 12 times	15	5.1
Total	296	100
Micronutrient Supplementation		
Did your child receive vitamin A supplement at 6 months?		
Yes	251	85.4
No	43	14.5
Total	294	100
Do you include varieties of food in your child diet?		
Yes	266	89.9
No	30	10.1
Total	296	100
Home Management of Infections		
Do you take your baby to hospital of symptoms refuse to stop after home management?		
Yes	291	98.3
No	5	1.7
Total	296	100

Mothers Practices on Seven Key Child Survival Interventions

How did you manage fever at home?		
Remove cloth and tepid sponge with lukewarm water	19	6.3
Remove cloth and mop the body with warm water	22	7.3
Bath with warm water and give paracetamol	30	10
Bath with cool water	49	16.3
Bath with cool water and give paracetamol	33	11
Give Anti-malaria drug and take to the hospital	7	2.3
Give Anti-biotics	1	0.3
Give paracetamol	89	29.6
Give paracetamol and blood tonic	2	0.6
Give paracetamol and take the child to hospital	5	1.7
Use insecticide treated nets	1	0.3
Wrap soaked towel in cool water around the baby body	3	1
Tepid sponge and expose the child to fresh air and give paracetamol	4	1.2
Take the child to the hospital	12	4
Soaked towel inside cool water and use to mop the child body and give paracetamol	21	7
Remove cloth, open nearby window and tepid with sponge	2	0.6
Give herbs	2	0.6
Total	300	100
How do you manage diarrhea at home?		
Give ORS	136	47.1
Give 7 key drug	1	0.3
Give breastmilk and ORS	23	8
Give 7 up drinks with salt	1	0.3
Give drug	88	30
Give herbs	2	0.7
Give lime water to the child	3	1
Give clean water and wash is eating utensils	2	0.7
Give malaria drug	3	1
Give ORS, use seven up instead of water	1	0.3
Give ORS and take to the hospital	2	0.7
Give ORS with zinc tablet	7	2.4
Give warm water to the child and drug	2	0.7
Give salt and water solution	3	1
Take child to chemist	1	0.3
Take the child to the hospital	14	4.8
Total	289	100

Mothers Practices on Seven Key Child Survival Interventions

How do you manage cough at home?		
Cover the chest with cloth and give cough drug	5	1.7
Give adequate breastmilk and water	1	0.3
Give breastmilk and honey	1	0.3
Give cough drug	195	66.8
Give cough drug and take the child to the hospital	21	7.3
Give herbal preparation	1	0.3
Give honey	5	1.7
Give honey and bitter kola	1	0.3
Give honey and cough drug	2	0.7
Give hot water and cover the child body	4	1.4
Give hot water with Eucalyptus oil	1	0.3
Warm water	18	6.3
Warm water and allum	1	0.3
Give warm water and honey	9	3.1
Give warm water and give cough drug	2	0.7
Give warm water and give breastmilk	2	0.7
Give lime water and honey	1	0.3
Give vitamin C	2	0.7
Rub the baby chest with rob	4	1.4
Rub the baby chest with rob and give cough drug	1	0.3
Take to the chemist	1	0.3
Take the child to the hospital	14	4.8
Total	292	100
Oral Rehydration Therapy		
Do you prepare ORS at home		
Yes	127	42.3
No	173	57.7
Total	300	100
Do you discard ORS 24 hours after preparation?		
Yes	151	50.5
No	148	49.5
Total	299	100
Insecticide Treated Nets		
Do you and your baby sleep under insecticide treated net?		
Yes	269	89.7
No	31	10.3
Total	300	100
Do you use insecticide treated net to prevent malaria?		
Yes	273	91
No	27	9
Total	300	100
If NO specify?		
Bath with herbal preparation	2	15.4
Give Ant-Malaria drug	5	38.5
Mosquito net at the door post and mosquito raid	3	23.1
Spread the insecticide treated on the window	3	23
Total	13	100

Table 9: Child Vaccination

VACCINE	COMPLETE	INCOMPLETE	DIDN'T TAKE	COMPLETE BUT NOT AT BIRTH	NOT APPLICABLE
BCG	282(94)	1(0.3)	3(1)	14(4.8)	-
DPT	157(52.3)	118(39.3)	1(0.3)	-	24(8.0)
PENTAVELENT	157(52.3)	118(39.3)	1(0.3)	-	24(8.0)
OPV	157(52.3)	118(39.3)	1(0.3)	-	24(8.0)
MEASLES/YELLOW FEVER	62(20.7)	1(0.3)	-	-	237(79.0)

Table 10: shows that the seven key child survival interventions on mother's knowledge has a significant association with the mother's practices on seven key child survival intervention having the P-value <0.05 .

Table 11: Show that there is signification relationship between weight for age of the children and the attitude of mother on babies should be fed with other food apart from breast milk at 6 months having a P-value of 0.05

Table 12: It was observed in this study that there is a significant association between the weight for age of the children and the attitude of mothers on insecticide treated net can prevent malaria having the P valve < 0.05 .

Table 13: A significant association was found between the nutritional status of the children (weight for height index) and attitude of mothers on a child with diarrhea should be withdraw from breast milk having the P-value < 0.05

Table 14: The result show there is a significant association between the nutritional status of the children (weight for height index) with the knowledge of mothers on breast milk have enough water and nutrient to meet the needs of the baby less than 6 months having the P-value <0.05

Table 15: A significant association was observed between the nutritional status of the children (weight for age index) and the practices of mothers on do they prepare Oral rehydration solution having a P-value <0.05

Table 10: Association between Knowledge and Practices of Mothers on Seven Key Child Survival Interventions.

KNOWLEDGE N (%)	PRACTICE N (%)			TOTAL	X2	PVALUE
	POOR	MODERATE	GOOD			
POOR	4(1.3)	9(3)	0(0)	13(4.3)	91.983 ^a	0.000
MODERATE	26(8.6)	121(40.3)	21(7)	168(56)		
GOOD	6(1.3)	40(1.3)	76(25.3)	119(39.6)		
TOTAL	34(11.3)	140(46.6)	96(32)	300(100)		

Table 11: Association between Weight for Age and Babies should be Fed with Other Food Apart from Breastmilk at 6 Month

ATTITUDE		WEIGHT FOR AGE (%)				TOTAL	X2	PVALUE
		MILD	MODERATE	SEVERE	NORMAL			
Babies should be fed with other food apart from breast milk at 6 month	UNDECIDED	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)	9(3)	9(3)	20.995 ^a	0.05
	STRONGLY DISAGREE	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)	4(1.3)	4(1.3)		
	DISAGREE	7(2.3)	2(0.6)	4(1.3)	9(3)	22(7.3)		
	AGREE	45(15)	18(6)	5(1.6)	100(33.3)	126(42)		
	STRONGLY AGREE	29(9.6)	10(3.3)	5(1.6)	53(17.6)	97(32.3)		
TOTAL		81(27)	30(10)	14(4.6)	175(58.3)	300(100)		

Table 12: Association between Weight for Age and Attitude on Insecticide Treated Net can Prevent Malaria.

ATTITUDE		WEIGHT FOR AGE				TOTAL	X2	PVALUE
		MILD	MODERATE	SEVERE	NORMAL			
INT can prevent Malaria	UNDECIDED	1(0.3)	0(0)	0(0)	2(0.6)	3(1)	29.564^a	0.003
	STRONGLY	1(0.3)	0(0)	0(0)	1(0.3)	2(0.6)		
	DISAGREE							
	DISAGREE	0(0)	0(0)	2(0.6)	1(0.3)	3(1)		
	AGREE	29(9.6)	13(4.3)	3(1)	73(24.3)	118(39.3)		
	STRONGLY	50(16.6)	17(5.6)	9(3)	98(32.6)	174(58)		
	AGREEE							
TOTAL		81(27)	30(10)	14(4.6)	175(58.3)	300(100)		

Table 13: Association between the Weight for Height and the Attitude of Mother on a Child with Diarrhea should be Withdraw from Breast Milk.

ATTITUDE		WEIGHT FOR HEIGHT				TOTAL	X2	PVALUE
		MILD	MODERATE	SEVERE	NORMAL			
A child with diarrhea should be withdrawn from breast milk	UNDECIDED	4(1.3)	3(1)	1(0.3)	3(1)	11(3.7)	29.564^a	0.017
	STRONGLY	3(1)	0(0)	1(0.3)	5(1.7)	9(3.0)		
	AGREE							
	AGREE	2(0.6)	0(0)	1(0.3)	21(7.2)	24(8.2)		
	DISAGREE	20(6.8)	6(2.0)	6(2.0)	86(29.5)	118(40.5)		
	STRONGLY	13(4.6)	12(4.1)	5(1.7)	99(34)	129(44.3)		
	DISAGREEE							
TOTAL		42(14.4)	21(7.2)	14(4.8)	214(73.5)	291(100)		

Table 14: Association between the Nutritional Status (Weight For Height Index) with Mothers Knowledge

KNOWLEDGE	WEIGHT FOR HEIGHT N (%)					TOTAL	X2	PVALUE
	MILD	MODERATE	SEVERE	NORMAL				
Does breast milk have enough water and nutrient to meet the needs of the baby less than 6 month	YES	77(25.6)	23(7.6)	14(4.6)	167(55.6)	271(90.3)	10.06^a	0.018
	NO	4(1.3)	7(2.3)	0(0)	18(6)	29(9.6)		
TOTAL		81(27)	30(10)	14(4.6)	175(58.3)	300(100)		

Table 15: Association between Nutritional Status (Weight for Age Index) of the Children with the Practices of Mothers.

PRACTICE	WEIGHT FOR AGE N (%)						X ²	PVALUE
		MILD	MODERATE	SEVERE	NORMAL	TOTAL		
Do you prepare ORS at home	YES	24(8)	12(4)	6(2)	85(28.3)	127(42.3)	8.213 ^a	0.042
	NO	57(19)	18(6)	8(2.6)	90(30)	172(57.3)		
TOTAL		81(27)	30(10)	14(4.6)	175(58.3)	300(100)		

4.2 DISCUSSION

Early and Exclusive Breastfeeding

The recommendation of World health organization (WHO) was that breastfeeding should be initiated within 30 minutes of child birth, however in this study 45.5% of the mothers give breast milk to their children within 30 minutes of child birth and 52.7% of the mothers have the knowledge of commencing breastfeeding within 30 minutes of child birth. Early initiation of breastfeeding serves as the starting point for the continuum of care for the mothers and new born that can have long effects on health and development (WHO, 2008). The study revealed high percentage of mother has knowledge about exclusively breastfeeding 76.3%. The prevalence of exclusive breastfeeding practices was 64.3%, this is similar to the finding of Sanusi and Gbadamosi, (2000) which reported that 67% of mothers practices exclusively breastfeeding in Ibadan, Oyo State and it lower than the finding reported in Ethiopia, 82% of mothers practices exclusive breastfeeding in the study conducted among mothers to assess their knowledge and practices of exclusive breastfeeding (Zenebu *et al.*, 2015).

From the study 35.7% of the mothers did not practices exclusive breastfeeding, due the believe that breastmilk does not have enough water to meet the needs of babies less than 6 months. 11.7% disagree that breastmilk have enough water, 15.2% agree that water, herbs and soft drink should be given to babies less than 6 months.

Appropriate Complementary Feeding

The study show that 33.7% of the mothers have the knowledge of feeding their children with enriched pap as complementary foods, while 19% of the mother as started introducing family diet to their children as complementary foods, the result is lower that the study carried out by Ndikwelu and Maduforo *et al.*, (2014) which reported that 72.5% of the mothers introduced family diet and 62.5% gave pap with milk as complementary feed while 2.5% gave plain pap.

The study also show that 75.7% of the mothers included varieties of food including fruit and vegetable in their children diet, 68% of the mothers introduced complementary food to their children at age 6 months and large percentage of the mothers 75% fed their babies 2–3 times daily also about one tenth 11.7% of the mothers fed their children 4–5 times daily.

Immunization

According to Centre for disease control and prevention (2011), most vaccine in the childhood immunization schedule requires two or more doses for development of an adequate and persisting antibody response. In this study, half 52.3% of the respondent had completed the immunization schedule for their children 1 months to 12 months at the time of this study this is higher than the findings of Oladipo and Ejembi (2013) in Kaduna State, which reported 23% of the nursing mothers completed the immunization schedule for their children. Whereas, in a study to assess mothers' practice of childhood immunization in Enugu State, Tagbo *et al.*, (2014) reported that 95.2% of the mothers took their children to health facilities for routine immunization.

According to Rahji and Ndikom (2013) in a study carried out in Ibadan, they reported that 80.4% of nursing mothers had taken vaccines at least once for their children. In this study, majority 95.3% of the mothers have the knowledge of given immunization at birth to their babies, 46% of the mothers have the knowledge of type of vaccines to be given at birth, also 48% of the mothers have the knowledge of when a child should complete immunization. A large percentage of mothers (79.7%) have the knowledge that immunization does not have advice effect on the children and 94% of the children received immunization at birth. 52.3% of the children have completed their immunization for DPT, PENTAVELENT and OPV while 20.7% of the children complete for Measles, however, this result of the present study conflicted National Population Commission & ORC Macro (2004) report that only 13% of

children ages 12-13 months could be considered fully immunized in Nigeria (i.e., have received BCG, three doses each of the DPT and polio excluding the polio given at birth and measles vaccines).

However, according to National population commission (2014), the prevalence of immunization was only 25% at the time the survey, although it was reported that in Ogun state, over 56.9% of the mothers completed the DPT vaccines for their children while 33% completed the polio vaccines. According to the study that was carried out in Kenya among nursing mothers Makau, reported that about all 92.9% of the respondent took their children for immunization. UNICEF (2001) had shown that Nigeria's immunization rates are among the worst in the world. Findings pertaining to immunization coverage in this study showed 94% of all the children had BCG vaccine which is similar to the find observed in this research, this was much higher than the 69% reported for Nigeria (UNICEF, 2001). Also 80.4% had one dose and 49.2% had three doses of DPT and oral polio vaccine and. This was higher than the corresponding figure of 72% and 54% for Nigeria (UNICEF, 2001).

Insecticide Treated Nets

Majority 89.7% of the mothers and babies use insecticide treated net, this is higher than study conducted in the North Western part of Nigeria, the use of insecticide treated net by the respondents was reported to be 57% (Sani *et al.*, 2014). However, in a study conducted in the Eastern part of Nigeria among mothers, the use of insecticide treated nets was just 11.7% (Iloh *et al.*, 2013). In this study 63.7% of the mothers have the knowledge of babies and mothers sleep under insecticide treated net and 93.3% of the mothers have the knowledge that insecticide treated net can prevent malaria. In another study conducted in Anambra (South East), it was reported that 44% of the respondents used insecticide treated nets of which only 23% used it always and 23% used it sometimes (Solomon *et al.*, 2014). However, according

to the study conducted in Calabar by Eyong Abiodun (2016), 64.77% of the respondents had under 5 children but only (49.12%) households had their under 5 years children utilizing bed nets/ITNs. The proportion of under five children sleeping under nets is higher in Calabar Municipality (25.96%) than in Calabar South (23.14%). According to National population commission (2014) statistics which shows that 55% of the household have at least one mosquito net and 50% have at least one insecticide treated net. Steven-Edemba (2014) in his assessment of vitamin A status of under-five children in Abuja, Nigeria reported that 79% of the children slept inside insecticide treated net.

Oral Rehydration Solution

Oral rehydration therapy is one of the child survival strategies introduced by the World Health Organization to reduce infant mortality which results from dehydration. Less than half 42.3% of the respondent use Oral rehydration therapy as home management of diarrhea, this is similar to the study conducted in Ibadan on the knowledge and use of Oral rehydration therapy among mothers of under-five children, it was reported that 49.5% of the mothers used oral rehydration solution to manage diarrhoea among their children, (Agbolade et al., 2015). In another study conducted in Rivers State, 43.5% of the respondents claimed to have used oral rehydration therapy for the management of diarrhoea (Osonwa et al., 2016). The result in this study is also lower than the result reported in another study conducted in Oyo by Rasaki and Ahani (2009), reported that 98.7% of the mothers have the knowledge of ORS while the study reveal that 77.9% have adequate knowledge of ORT across all age groups of the mothers and 78.3% rate of utilization. In the study 14.3% of the mothers have the correct knowledge of preparing ORS at home whereas 42.3% of the mothers have the knowledge of discarding the ORS 24 hours after preparation and 50.3% of the mothers discard the preparation of the ORS 24 hours after preparation.

According to Nigeria Demographic and Health Survey (2013) statistics on the use of oral rehydration therapy for the management of diarrhoea among children by mothers, it was reported that the prevalence on the use of oral rehydration therapy was 43.6% in the South Western part of the country.

Adequate Micronutrients through Diet and Supplementation

In this study 87.3% of the children received Vitamin A supplement, this is higher than the study conducted in Admmawa State, Tyndall *et al.*, (2012) reported that 68% of the respondents took vitamin supplements for their children and also similar to the finding of Steve-Edemba, (2014), in his assessment of vitamin A status of under-five children in Abuja, Nigeria reported that 84.5% of the children were given vitamin A supplements. According to National Population Commission (2013) statistics, it was reported that the use of vitamin supplements by nursing mothers among under-five children in Nigeria was forty-one percent

However, in this study, 45.3% of the respondents, have the knowledge of the capsules given to children at age 6 months (Vitamin A) and about 95.3% of the mothers include varieties of food in their children diet including fruits and vegetable, the reason in high variation of the result, might be as a result of nutrition education given to mothers on the immunization and clinic days and also as result that, the mothers involved are those that attended primary health care center in the community. In a study carried out in Kenya to assess the feeding practices and nutritional status of children aged 0-59 months of age, it was reported that 71.8% of the mothers gave vitamin supplements to their children (Makau, 2013). Gebremedhin (2009) reported that 81.3% of the respondents gave vitamin supplements to their children in his study on the assessment of vitamin A supplements among mothers in Ethiopia.

Home Management of Infection

It was observed in the study that 53.7% of the mothers have the knowledge of given oral rehydration solution to babies having diarrhea at home and 77% of the mothers have the knowledge of not withdrawing breast milk from the child that is having diarrhea.

In a study conducted in Ibadan on the knowledge and use of Oral rehydration therapy among mothers of under-five children, it was reported that 49.5% of the mothers used oral rehydration solution to manage diarrhoea among their children, (Agbolade et al., 2015). In another study conducted in Rivers State, 43.5% of the respondents claimed to have used oral rehydration therapy for the management of diarrhoea (Osonwa et al., 2016). However, Sanusi and Gbadamosi (2009) reported a higher prevalence (78.3%) of oral rehydration therapy use by nursing mothers in Ibadan. The study is similar to Adrawa (2011) in his study on Oral rehydration salt solution use among under-five children in Uganda, he reported that 64.6% of the mothers used oral rehydration solution for their children. In 2007, only 31% of under-five children in Africa were given oral rehydration solution (World Vision, 2010).

The study also shows that 48.7% of the mothers have the knowledge of removing clothes, sponge with lukewarm water for babies that is having fever at home also, 92.7% of the mothers have the knowledge of given paracetamol and taking the child to the hospital is children having fever at home, about 95% of the mothers have the knowledge of taking their children to hospital is symptom persist after home management. It was observed that 45.3% of the mothers give ORS to their children and about 15.3% of the mother gives warm water, breast milk, honey to their children has remedy to cough at home.

Attitude of Mothers on Seven Key Child Survival Intervention

The study shows that mothers have positive and negative attitude towards seven key child survival interventions.

The mean of these attitudinal questions, Should mother commence breastfeeding within 30 minutes after child birth, Should an infant be exclusively breastfed for 6 months, Does breast milk has enough water and nutrients to meet the needs of babies less than 6 months, Babies should be fed with other food apart from breast milk at 6 months, Infant should be fed up 3-5 times daily, The diet of a child should contain varieties of food including fruits and vegetables, INT can prevent malaria, A child with diarrhea should be withdrawn from breast milk, Babies and mothers shouldn't sleep under Insecticide treated net, is above 3 (mean value greater than 3) showing that mothers have positive attitudes towards these questions.

The mean of these attitudinal questions, Water, herbs and soft drinks should be given to infant less than 6 months, A child less than 6 months should be given other food apart from breast milk, Should fruits and vegetable be given to babies receiving complementary foods, Breast milk shouldn't be given to babies alongside with complementary foods, Family diet should be introduced as complementary foods, At Age 6 months, Vitamin A should be given to infant, Babies shouldn't be given immunization at birth, Babies should receive immunization 6 times, Babies should complete immunization at 12 months, Water salt and sugar are constituent of ORS, ORS should be discarded 24 hours after preparation, Should ORS be given to infant as soon as diarrhea starts, Diarrhea affecting babies at home can be managed by given ORS, Breast milk, warm water with honey should be given as cough management at home, A child with fever at should be given anti-malaria and not taking to hospital, is below 3 (mean value less than 3) showing that mothers have negative attitude towards these question.

More than half 58% strongly agree that Insecticide treated net can prevent malaria, which is similar to the study conducted by San *et al.*,(2013) in Malaysia which reported that 52.0% correctly perceived that malaria could be prevented even if one is residing in malaria also in the study 51.2% disagree that babies and mothers should not sleep under insecticide treated net while in the study conducted by San *et al.*,(2013) 54.3% correctly perceived that malaria could be prevented if one is sleeping inside mosquito net and 86.7% correctly believed that sleeping inside ITN at night reduces mosquito bite.

Seven Key Child Survival Interventions and the Nutritional Status of the Children.

The seven key child survival intervention by the mothers' knowledge, attitude and practices does not have significant association with the nutritional status of the children.

In this study there is significant association between the over all knowledge and practices of mother on seven key child survival intervention, San *et al.*,(2013) reported that there was significant association between knowledge and practices of mothers. However, mothers attitude, such as babies should be fed with other food apart from breastmilk at 6 month, insecticide treated net can prevent malaria, a child with diarrhea should be withdraw from breastmilk, has significant association with the weight for age of the children and weight for height of the children which was similarly reported by San *et al.*, (2013) that there was significant association between attitude of mothers and nutritional status of the children.

The study also revealed that mother knowledge, does breastmilk have enough water and nutrient to meet the need of the baby less than 6 months has significant association with the weight for height of the children. Also the mother practices, Do you prepare ORS at home significantly affect the weight for age of the children. It was also reported that the practice of child survival strategies was significantly related with wasting among the children (Abasiattai *et al.*, 2014; Akorede and Abiola, 2013).

Nutrition Status of the Children

The prevalence of malnutrition that was observed in these is 11.7%, 22.4%, 14.7% for wasting, stunting and underweight respectively this is lower than the finding by Sanusi and Gbadamosi (2009) in Ibadan which reported that the prevalence of wasting, stunting and underweight was 22%, 68% and 63.3% respectively. 11.7% of the children are stunted and 10.7% are moderately stunted, also 4.7% of the children are severely wasted and 7.0% of the children are moderately wasted. In this present result is different from the study conducted in Oyo by Rasaki *et al.*, (2009) reported that, the prevalence of stunting is highest in the children but a clear trend cannot be recognized: while proportion of wasted children increased with maternal age, 68% of the children were stunted with 41.3% severe, 63.3% underweight with 7.1% severe and 22% wasted with 7.1% severe. However, in another study carried out in the Northern part of the country, 44.9%, 15.6% and 3.7% were respectively stunted, underweight and wasted (Aliyu *et al.*, 2012).

CHAPTER FIVE

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

5.1 Conclusion

This study revealed that mother have moderate knowledge on the seven key child survival intervention, and the practices on seven key child survival intervention was low in comparison with the level of their knowledge on the seven key child survival intervention. Some mothers have low knowledge on some key intervention such as Oral rehydration therapy, immunization, what capsule to be given at 6 months, despite the nutrition education on daily immunization clinic days. The result also shows here is negative attitude towards some key child survival intervention. Moreover, there were cases of malnutrition among the children. There is high prevalence of wasting, stunting and underweight respectively. The study revealed that there is significant relationship between the knowledge and practices of mothers on seven key child survival interventions. Association was found between some knowledge, practices and attitude of mother to the nutritional status of the children.

5.2.1 Recommendation

Based on the findings of this study, these recommendations will enhance the knowledge, attitude and practice of mothers on these seven key child survival interventions.

Health workers should place more emphasis on helping the mothers in raising their critical consciousness, also reorient the mothers on benefits and their wrong attitude toward these interventions which may affect the nutritional status of their children. The health care worker should encourage the mothers in cases of challenges in their bid to practice. Government should ensure that every primary health center have a Nutritionist or Dieticians and also give out incentive to mothers that practice these interventions to encourage more practices.

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